

General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares

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Abstract

The idea of nested magic squares are well known in the literature, generally known by bordered magic squares. In this paper, we worked with general sum for the nested magic squares. Considering the idea of magic sum 0 from the H. White's site [1], the nested magic squares are studied in different situations. The work is for the orders from 20 to 3. Symmetric positive nested magic squares are also studied.

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1 Introduction

Let's consider following two **nested magic squares** of orders 20 and 19 obtained from the site by H. White [1].

Example 1. *Nested magic square of order 20 with **positive-negative** entries written in a symmetric way with magic sum 0 is given by*

																			0	
-181.5	170.5	-169.5	168.5	-167.5	166.5	-165.5	164.5	-163.5	162.5	199.5	191.5	-192.5	193.5	-194.5	195.5	-196.5	197.5	-198.5	-180.5	0
189.5	144.5	-137.5	138.5	-139.5	140.5	-141.5	142.5	-143.5	153.5	-161.5	146.5	-147.5	148.5	-149.5	150.5	-151.5	152.5	-145.5	-189.5	0
-188.5	135.5	113.5	-106.5	107.5	-108.5	-109.5	110.5	111.5	120.5	105.5	-114.5	-115.5	116.5	-117.5	118.5	-119.5	-112.5	-135.5	188.5	0
187.5	-134.5	126.5	-84.5	-90.5	89.5	-88.5	87.5	-86.5	97.5	-91.5	83.5	-82.5	81.5	-80.5	79.5	85.5	-126.5	134.5	-187.5	0
-186.5	133.5	-125.5	96.5	61.5	70.5	-69.5	68.5	-67.5	-71.5	-50.5	51.5	-52.5	53.5	-54.5	60.5	-96.5	125.5	-133.5	186.5	0
185.5	-132.5	124.5	-95.5	-56.5	40.5	35.5	-34.5	33.5	-32.5	-36.5	-46.5	47.5	-48.5	41.5	56.5	95.5	-124.5	132.5	-185.5	0
-184.5	131.5	-123.5	94.5	-57.5	-37.5	-24.5	-30.5	29.5	31.5	18.5	-19.5	20.5	-25.5	37.5	57.5	-94.5	123.5	-131.5	184.5	0
183.5	-130.5	122.5	-93.5	58.5	38.5	-27.5	13.5	11.5	-15.5	17.5	-14.5	-12.5	27.5	-38.5	-58.5	93.5	-122.5	130.5	-183.5	0
182.5	129.5	-121.5	92.5	59.5	-39.5	-26.5	-16.5	5.5	-7.5	-4.5	6.5	16.5	26.5	39.5	-59.5	-92.5	121.5	-129.5	-182.5	0
-171.5	-128.5	-127.5	78.5	66.5	45.5	-21.5	-10.5	-1.5	3.5	0.5	-2.5	10.5	21.5	-45.5	-66.5	-78.5	127.5	128.5	171.5	0
-190.5	-136.5	-98.5	72.5	55.5	-49.5	28.5	-8.5	2.5	-0.5	-3.5	1.5	8.5	-28.5	49.5	-55.5	-72.5	98.5	136.5	190.5	0
-179.5	-154.5	99.5	-73.5	-62.5	42.5	23.5	9.5	-6.5	4.5	7.5	-5.5	-9.5	-23.5	-42.5	62.5	73.5	-99.5	154.5	179.5	0
-178.5	155.5	-100.5	74.5	-63.5	-43.5	22.5	12.5	-11.5	15.5	-17.5	14.5	-13.5	-22.5	43.5	63.5	-74.5	100.5	-155.5	178.5	0
177.5	-156.5	101.5	-75.5	64.5	44.5	25.5	30.5	-29.5	-31.5	-18.5	19.5	-20.5	24.5	-44.5	-64.5	75.5	-101.5	156.5	-177.5	0
176.5	157.5	-102.5	76.5	-65.5	-41.5	-35.5	34.5	-33.5	32.5	36.5	46.5	-47.5	48.5	-40.5	65.5	-76.5	102.5	-157.5	-176.5	0
-175.5	-158.5	103.5	-77.5	-60.5	-70.5	69.5	-68.5	67.5	71.5	50.5	-51.5	52.5	-53.5	54.5	-61.5	77.5	-103.5	158.5	175.5	0
174.5	159.5	-104.5	-85.5	90.5	-89.5	88.5	-87.5	86.5	-97.5	91.5	-83.5	82.5	-81.5	80.5	-79.5	84.5	104.5	-159.5	-174.5	0
-173.5	-160.5	112.5	106.5	-107.5	108.5	109.5	-110.5	-111.5	-120.5	-105.5	114.5	115.5	-116.5	117.5	-118.5	119.5	-113.5	160.5	173.5	0
172.5	145.5	137.5	-138.5	139.5	-140.5	141.5	-142.5	143.5	-153.5	161.5	-146.5	147.5	-148.5	149.5	-150.5	151.5	-152.5	-144.5	-172.5	0
180.5	-170.5	169.5	-168.5	167.5	-166.5	165.5	-164.5	163.5	-162.5	-199.5	-191.5	192.5	-193.5	194.5	-195.5	196.5	-197.5	198.5	181.5	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

The entries of above nested magic square are

$$\{0, \pm 0.5, \pm 1.5, \pm 2.5, \dots, \pm 189.5\}$$

In this case the sub-magic squares sums are also zero, i.e.,

$$S_{k \times k} := 0; \quad k = 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18 \text{ and } 20.$$

Decimal values are considered to bring magic sums as 0. It is due to symmetric entries as shown above.

Example 2. Nested magic square of order 19 with *positive-negative* entries written in a symmetric way with magic square sum 0 is given by

																			0
-161	-145	-147	-149	-151	-153	-155	-157	-159	164	165	167	169	171	173	175	177	179	-163	0
180	-129	143	141	139	137	135	133	131	130	-125	-123	-121	-119	-117	-115	-113	-127	-180	0
178	-144	97	86	88	90	92	94	96	98	-102	-104	-106	-108	-110	-112	-99	144	-178	0
176	-142	-111	71	62	64	66	68	70	72	-76	-78	-80	-82	-84	-73	111	142	-176	0
174	-140	-109	-83	-49	-41	-43	-45	-47	52	53	55	57	59	-51	83	109	140	-174	0
172	-138	-107	-81	60	-33	39	37	35	34	-29	-27	-25	-31	-60	81	107	138	-172	0
170	-136	-105	-79	58	-40	-17	-13	-15	20	21	23	-19	40	-58	79	105	136	-170	0
168	-134	-103	-77	56	-38	24	-9	-12	8	6	7	-24	38	-56	77	103	134	-168	0
166	-132	-101	-75	54	-36	22	11	1	-4	3	-11	-22	36	-54	75	101	132	-166	0
-162	128	-100	-74	-50	32	-18	10	2	0	-2	-10	18	-32	50	74	100	-128	162	0
-160	126	95	69	-48	30	-16	-5	-3	4	-1	5	16	-30	48	-69	-95	-126	160	0
-158	124	93	67	-46	28	-14	-7	12	-8	-6	9	14	-28	46	-67	-93	-124	158	0
-156	122	91	65	-44	26	19	13	15	-20	-21	-23	17	-26	44	-65	-91	-122	156	0
-154	120	89	63	-42	31	-39	-37	-35	-34	29	27	25	33	42	-63	-89	-120	154	0
-152	118	87	61	51	41	43	45	47	-52	-53	-55	-57	-59	49	-61	-87	-118	152	0
-150	116	85	73	-62	-64	-66	-68	-70	-72	76	78	80	82	84	-71	-85	-116	150	0
-148	114	99	-86	-88	-90	-92	-94	-96	-98	102	104	106	108	110	112	-97	-114	148	0
-146	127	-143	-141	-139	-137	-135	-133	-131	-130	125	123	121	119	117	115	113	129	146	0
163	145	147	149	151	153	155	157	159	-164	-165	-167	-169	-171	-173	-175	-177	-179	161	0
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

The entries of above nested magic square are

$$\{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \dots, \pm 180\}$$

In this case the sub-magic square sums are also zero, i.e.,

$$S_{k \times k} := 0; k = 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 17 \text{ and } 19.$$

It is well-known that the magic sum of magic square of order n formed by consecutive natural numbers $\{1, 2, \dots, n^2 - 1, n^2\}$ is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n(n^2 + 1)}{2} \quad (1)$$

The formula given in (1) shall be used frequently in this work.

There are many types of **bordered magic squares**. Here we are working with bordered magic squares, where there are sub-magic squares one contained in another. Due to this we called this category as **nested magic squares**. For study in this direction, refer to [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 10, 11, 12].

The aim of this work is to write nested magic squares for any general value with possible sub-groups. In the case the magic square sums are also given. As a particular case, the positive values nested magic squares of even and odd orders are also given. At the end the particular examples of the general case are also given. Moreover, the study can be extended to further orders. Just as a simplicity, we considered nested magic squares of orders 19 and 20. Recent, study on nested magic squares can be seen in Walkington[6] and Taneja [10, 11, 12, 13].

2 Nested Magic Squares

Below are even and odd order **nested magic squares** with final sum n . This we have done for the magic squares of order 20 to 3 (decreasing order).

2.1 Nested Magic Square of Order 20

Add each term of magic square of order 20 given in Example (1) by $n/20$, where $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer). This gives

Result 1. *Nested magic square of order 20 with **symmetric entries** and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by*

-181.5+.05n	170.5+.05n	-169.5+.05n	168.5+.05n	-167.5+.05n	166.5+.05n	-165.5+.05n	164.5+.05n	-163.5+.05n	162.5+.05n	199.5+.05n	191.5+.05n	-192.5+.05n	193.5+.05n	-194.5+.05n	195.5+.05n	-196.5+.05n	197.5+.05n	-198.5+.05n	-180.5+.05n	n
189.5+.05n	144.5+.05n	-137.5+.05n	138.5+.05n	-139.5+.05n	140.5+.05n	-141.5+.05n	142.5+.05n	-143.5+.05n	153.5+.05n	-161.5+.05n	146.5+.05n	-147.5+.05n	148.5+.05n	-149.5+.05n	150.5+.05n	-151.5+.05n	152.5+.05n	-145.5+.05n	-189.5+.05n	n
-188.5+.05n	135.5+.05n	113.5+.05n	-106.5+.05n	107.5+.05n	-108.5+.05n	-109.5+.05n	110.5+.05n	111.5+.05n	120.5+.05n	105.5+.05n	-114.5+.05n	-115.5+.05n	116.5+.05n	-117.5+.05n	118.5+.05n	-119.5+.05n	-112.5+.05n	-135.5+.05n	188.5+.05n	n
187.5+.05n	-134.5+.05n	126.5+.05n	-84.5+.05n	-90.5+.05n	89.5+.05n	-88.5+.05n	87.5+.05n	-86.5+.05n	97.5+.05n	-91.5+.05n	83.5+.05n	-82.5+.05n	81.5+.05n	-80.5+.05n	79.5+.05n	85.5+.05n	-126.5+.05n	134.5+.05n	-187.5+.05n	n
-186.5+.05n	133.5+.05n	-125.5+.05n	96.5+.05n	61.5+.05n	70.5+.05n	-69.5+.05n	68.5+.05n	-67.5+.05n	-71.5+.05n	-50.5+.05n	51.5+.05n	-52.5+.05n	53.5+.05n	-54.5+.05n	60.5+.05n	-96.5+.05n	125.5+.05n	-133.5+.05n	186.5+.05n	n
185.5+.05n	-132.5+.05n	124.5+.05n	-95.5+.05n	-56.5+.05n	40.5+.05n	35.5+.05n	-34.5+.05n	33.5+.05n	-32.5+.05n	-36.5+.05n	-46.5+.05n	47.5+.05n	-48.5+.05n	41.5+.05n	56.5+.05n	95.5+.05n	-124.5+.05n	132.5+.05n	-185.5+.05n	n
-184.5+.05n	131.5+.05n	-123.5+.05n	94.5+.05n	-57.5+.05n	-37.5+.05n	-24.5+.05n	-30.5+.05n	29.5+.05n	31.5+.05n	18.5+.05n	-19.5+.05n	20.5+.05n	-25.5+.05n	37.5+.05n	57.5+.05n	-94.5+.05n	123.5+.05n	-131.5+.05n	184.5+.05n	n
183.5+.05n	-130.5+.05n	122.5+.05n	-93.5+.05n	58.5+.05n	38.5+.05n	-27.5+.05n	13.5+.05n	11.5+.05n	-15.5+.05n	17.5+.05n	-14.5+.05n	-12.5+.05n	27.5+.05n	-38.5+.05n	-58.5+.05n	93.5+.05n	-122.5+.05n	130.5+.05n	-183.5+.05n	n
182.5+.05n	129.5+.05n	-121.5+.05n	92.5+.05n	59.5+.05n	-39.5+.05n	-26.5+.05n	-16.5+.05n	5.5+.05n	-7.5+.05n	-4.5+.05n	6.5+.05n	16.5+.05n	26.5+.05n	39.5+.05n	-59.5+.05n	-92.5+.05n	121.5+.05n	-129.5+.05n	-182.5+.05n	n
-171.5+.05n	-128.5+.05n	-127.5+.05n	78.5+.05n	66.5+.05n	45.5+.05n	-21.5+.05n	-10.5+.05n	-1.5+.05n	3.5+.05n	0.5+.05n	-2.5+.05n	10.5+.05n	21.5+.05n	-45.5+.05n	-66.5+.05n	-78.5+.05n	127.5+.05n	128.5+.05n	171.5+.05n	n
-190.5+.05n	-136.5+.05n	-98.5+.05n	72.5+.05n	55.5+.05n	-49.5+.05n	28.5+.05n	-8.5+.05n	2.5+.05n	-0.5+.05n	-3.5+.05n	1.5+.05n	8.5+.05n	-28.5+.05n	49.5+.05n	-55.5+.05n	-72.5+.05n	98.5+.05n	136.5+.05n	190.5+.05n	n
-179.5+.05n	-154.5+.05n	99.5+.05n	-73.5+.05n	-62.5+.05n	42.5+.05n	23.5+.05n	9.5+.05n	-6.5+.05n	4.5+.05n	7.5+.05n	-5.5+.05n	-9.5+.05n	-23.5+.05n	-42.5+.05n	62.5+.05n	73.5+.05n	-99.5+.05n	154.5+.05n	179.5+.05n	n
-178.5+.05n	155.5+.05n	-100.5+.05n	74.5+.05n	-63.5+.05n	-43.5+.05n	22.5+.05n	12.5+.05n	-11.5+.05n	15.5+.05n	-17.5+.05n	14.5+.05n	-13.5+.05n	-22.5+.05n	43.5+.05n	63.5+.05n	-74.5+.05n	100.5+.05n	-155.5+.05n	178.5+.05n	n
177.5+.05n	-156.5+.05n	101.5+.05n	-75.5+.05n	64.5+.05n	44.5+.05n	25.5+.05n	30.5+.05n	-29.5+.05n	-31.5+.05n	-18.5+.05n	19.5+.05n	-20.5+.05n	24.5+.05n	-44.5+.05n	-64.5+.05n	75.5+.05n	-101.5+.05n	156.5+.05n	-177.5+.05n	n
176.5+.05n	157.5+.05n	-102.5+.05n	76.5+.05n	-65.5+.05n	-41.5+.05n	-35.5+.05n	34.5+.05n	-33.5+.05n	32.5+.05n	36.5+.05n	46.5+.05n	-47.5+.05n	48.5+.05n	-40.5+.05n	65.5+.05n	-76.5+.05n	102.5+.05n	-157.5+.05n	-176.5+.05n	n
-175.5+.05n	-158.5+.05n	103.5+.05n	-77.5+.05n	-60.5+.05n	-70.5+.05n	69.5+.05n	-68.5+.05n	67.5+.05n	71.5+.05n	50.5+.05n	-51.5+.05n	52.5+.05n	-53.5+.05n	54.5+.05n	-61.5+.05n	77.5+.05n	-103.5+.05n	158.5+.05n	175.5+.05n	n
174.5+.05n	159.5+.05n	-104.5+.05n	-85.5+.05n	90.5+.05n	-89.5+.05n	88.5+.05n	-87.5+.05n	86.5+.05n	-97.5+.05n	91.5+.05n	-83.5+.05n	82.5+.05n	-81.5+.05n	80.5+.05n	-79.5+.05n	84.5+.05n	104.5+.05n	-159.5+.05n	-174.5+.05n	n
-173.5+.05n	-160.5+.05n	112.5+.05n	106.5+.05n	-107.5+.05n	108.5+.05n	109.5+.05n	-110.5+.05n	-111.5+.05n	-120.5+.05n	-105.5+.05n	114.5+.05n	115.5+.05n	-116.5+.05n	117.5+.05n	-118.5+.05n	119.5+.05n	-113.5+.05n	160.5+.05n	173.5+.05n	n
172.5+.05n	145.5+.05n	137.5+.05n	-138.5+.05n	139.5+.05n	-140.5+.05n	141.5+.05n	-142.5+.05n	143.5+.05n	-153.5+.05n	161.5+.05n	-146.5+.05n	147.5+.05n	-148.5+.05n	149.5+.05n	-150.5+.05n	151.5+.05n	-152.5+.05n	-144.5+.05n	-172.5+.05n	n
180.5+.05n	-170.5+.05n	169.5+.05n	-168.5+.05n	167.5+.05n	-166.5+.05n	165.5+.05n	-164.5+.05n	163.5+.05n	-162.5+.05n	-199.5+.05n	-191.5+.05n	192.5+.05n	-193.5+.05n	194.5+.05n	-195.5+.05n	196.5+.05n	-197.5+.05n	198.5+.05n	181.5+.05n	n
n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n

(2)

In this case, the magic sums are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4n}{20} = \frac{n}{5} & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12n}{20} = \frac{3n}{5} \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6n}{20} = \frac{3n}{10} & S_{14 \times 14} &:= \frac{14n}{20} = \frac{7n}{10} \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8n}{20} = \frac{2n}{5} & S_{16 \times 16} &:= \frac{16n}{20} = \frac{4n}{5} \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10n}{20} = \frac{n}{2} & S_{18 \times 18} &:= \frac{18n}{20} = \frac{9n}{10} \\
 & & S_{20 \times 20} &:= \frac{20n}{20} = n.
 \end{aligned}$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{\pm 0.5, \pm 1.5, \dots, \pm 198.5 \pm 199.5\}$.

Example 3. Let's consider $n = 134$ in (2), we get

-174.8	177.2	-162.8	175.2	-160.8	173.2	-158.8	171.2	-156.8	169.2	206.2	198.2	-185.8	200.2	-187.8	202.2	-189.8	204.2	-191.8	-173.8	134
196.2	151.2	-130.8	145.2	-132.8	147.2	-134.8	149.2	-136.8	160.2	-154.8	153.2	-140.8	155.2	-142.8	157.2	-144.8	159.2	-138.8	-182.8	134
-181.8	142.2	120.2	-99.8	114.2	-101.8	-102.8	117.2	118.2	127.2	112.2	-107.8	-108.8	123.2	-110.8	125.2	-112.8	-105.8	-128.8	195.2	134
194.2	-127.8	133.2	-77.8	-83.8	96.2	-81.8	94.2	-79.8	104.2	-84.8	90.2	-75.8	88.2	-73.8	86.2	92.2	-119.8	141.2	-180.8	134
-179.8	140.2	-118.8	103.2	68.2	77.2	-62.8	75.2	-60.8	-64.8	-43.8	58.2	-45.8	60.2	-47.8	67.2	-89.8	132.2	-126.8	193.2	134
192.2	-125.8	131.2	-88.8	-49.8	47.2	42.2	-27.8	40.2	-25.8	-29.8	-39.8	54.2	-41.8	48.2	63.2	102.2	-117.8	139.2	-178.8	134
-177.8	138.2	-116.8	101.2	-50.8	-30.8	-17.8	-23.8	36.2	38.2	25.2	-12.8	27.2	-18.8	44.2	64.2	-87.8	130.2	-124.8	191.2	134
190.2	-123.8	129.2	-86.8	65.2	45.2	-20.8	20.2	18.2	-8.8	24.2	-7.8	-5.8	34.2	-31.8	-51.8	100.2	-115.8	137.2	-176.8	134
189.2	136.2	-114.8	99.2	66.2	-32.8	-19.8	-9.8	12.2	-0.8	2.2	13.2	23.2	33.2	46.2	-52.8	-85.8	128.2	-122.8	-175.8	134
-164.8	-121.8	-120.8	85.2	73.2	52.2	-14.8	-3.8	5.2	10.2	7.2	4.2	17.2	28.2	-38.8	-59.8	-71.8	134.2	135.2	178.2	134
-183.8	-129.8	-91.8	79.2	62.2	-42.8	35.2	-1.8	9.2	6.2	3.2	8.2	15.2	-21.8	56.2	-48.8	-65.8	105.2	143.2	197.2	134
-172.8	-147.8	106.2	-66.8	-55.8	49.2	30.2	16.2	0.2	11.2	14.2	1.2	-2.8	-16.8	-35.8	69.2	80.2	-92.8	161.2	186.2	134
-171.8	162.2	-93.8	81.2	-56.8	-36.8	29.2	19.2	-4.8	22.2	-10.8	21.2	-6.8	-15.8	50.2	70.2	-67.8	107.2	-148.8	185.2	134
184.2	-149.8	108.2	-68.8	71.2	51.2	32.2	37.2	-22.8	-24.8	-11.8	26.2	-13.8	31.2	-37.8	-57.8	82.2	-94.8	163.2	-170.8	134
183.2	164.2	-95.8	83.2	-58.8	-34.8	-28.8	41.2	-26.8	39.2	43.2	53.2	-40.8	55.2	-33.8	72.2	-69.8	109.2	-150.8	-169.8	134
-168.8	-151.8	110.2	-70.8	-53.8	-63.8	76.2	-61.8	74.2	78.2	57.2	-44.8	59.2	-46.8	61.2	-54.8	84.2	-96.8	165.2	182.2	134
181.2	166.2	-97.8	-78.8	97.2	-82.8	95.2	-80.8	93.2	-90.8	98.2	-76.8	89.2	-74.8	87.2	-72.8	91.2	111.2	-152.8	-167.8	134
-166.8	-153.8	119.2	113.2	-100.8	115.2	116.2	-103.8	-104.8	-113.8	-98.8	121.2	122.2	-109.8	124.2	-111.8	126.2	-106.8	167.2	180.2	134
179.2	152.2	144.2	-131.8	146.2	-133.8	148.2	-135.8	150.2	-146.8	168.2	-139.8	154.2	-141.8	156.2	-143.8	158.2	-145.8	-137.8	-165.8	134
187.2	-163.8	176.2	-161.8	174.2	-159.8	172.2	-157.8	170.2	-155.8	-192.8	-184.8	199.2	-186.8	201.2	-188.8	203.2	-190.8	205.2	188.2	134
134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134	134

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4n}{20} = \frac{4 \times 134}{20} = 26.8 & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12n}{20} = \frac{12 \times 134}{20} = 80.4 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6n}{20} = \frac{6 \times 134}{20} = 40.2 & S_{14 \times 14} &:= \frac{14n}{20} = \frac{14 \times 134}{20} = 93.8 \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8n}{20} = \frac{8 \times 134}{20} = 53.6 & S_{16 \times 16} &:= \frac{16n}{20} = \frac{16 \times 134}{20} = 107.2 \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10n}{20} = \frac{10 \times 134}{20} = 67 & S_{18 \times 18} &:= \frac{18n}{20} = \frac{18 \times 134}{20} = 120.6 \\
 & & S_{20 \times 20} &:= 134.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 4. Let's consider $n = 136$ in (2), we get

136

-174.7	177.3	-162.7	175.3	-160.7	173.3	-158.7	171.3	-156.7	169.3	206.3	198.3	-185.7	200.3	-187.7	202.3	-189.7	204.3	-191.7	-173.7	136
196.3	151.3	-130.7	145.3	-132.7	147.3	-134.7	149.3	-136.7	160.3	-154.7	153.3	-140.7	155.3	-142.7	157.3	-144.7	159.3	-138.7	-182.7	136
-181.7	142.3	120.3	-99.7	114.3	-101.7	-102.7	117.3	118.3	127.3	112.3	-107.7	-108.7	123.3	-110.7	125.3	-112.7	-105.7	-128.7	195.3	136
194.3	-127.7	133.3	-77.7	-83.7	96.3	-81.7	94.3	-79.7	104.3	-84.7	90.3	-75.7	88.3	-73.7	86.3	92.3	-119.7	141.3	-180.7	136
-179.7	140.3	-118.7	103.3	68.3	77.3	-62.7	75.3	-60.7	-64.7	-43.7	58.3	-45.7	60.3	-47.7	67.3	-89.7	132.3	-126.7	193.3	136
192.3	-125.7	131.3	-88.7	-49.7	47.3	42.3	-27.7	40.3	-25.7	-29.7	-39.7	54.3	-41.7	48.3	63.3	102.3	-117.7	139.3	-178.7	136
-177.7	138.3	-116.7	101.3	-50.7	-30.7	-17.7	-23.7	36.3	38.3	25.3	-12.7	27.3	-18.7	44.3	64.3	-87.7	130.3	-124.7	191.3	136
190.3	-123.7	129.3	-86.7	65.3	45.3	-20.7	20.3	18.3	-8.7	24.3	-7.7	-5.7	34.3	-31.7	-51.7	100.3	-115.7	137.3	-176.7	136
189.3	136.3	-114.7	99.3	66.3	-32.7	-19.7	-9.7	12.3	-0.7	2.3	13.3	23.3	33.3	46.3	-52.7	-85.7	128.3	-122.7	-175.7	136
-164.7	-121.7	-120.7	85.3	73.3	52.3	-14.7	-3.7	5.3	10.3	7.3	4.3	17.3	28.3	-38.7	-59.7	-71.7	134.3	135.3	178.3	136
-183.7	-129.7	-91.7	79.3	62.3	-42.7	35.3	-1.7	9.3	6.3	3.3	8.3	15.3	-21.7	56.3	-48.7	-65.7	105.3	143.3	197.3	136
-172.7	-147.7	106.3	-66.7	-55.7	49.3	30.3	16.3	0.3	11.3	14.3	1.3	-2.7	-16.7	-35.7	69.3	80.3	-92.7	161.3	186.3	136
-171.7	162.3	-93.7	81.3	-56.7	-36.7	29.3	19.3	-4.7	22.3	-10.7	21.3	-6.7	-15.7	50.3	70.3	-67.7	107.3	-148.7	185.3	136
184.3	-149.7	108.3	-68.7	71.3	51.3	32.3	37.3	-22.7	-24.7	-11.7	26.3	-13.7	31.3	-37.7	-57.7	82.3	-94.7	163.3	-170.7	136
183.3	164.3	-95.7	83.3	-58.7	-34.7	-28.7	41.3	-26.7	39.3	43.3	53.3	-40.7	55.3	-33.7	72.3	-69.7	109.3	-150.7	-169.7	136
-168.7	-151.7	110.3	-70.7	-53.7	-63.7	76.3	-61.7	74.3	78.3	57.3	-44.7	59.3	-46.7	61.3	-54.7	84.3	-96.7	165.3	182.3	136
181.3	166.3	-97.7	-78.7	97.3	-82.7	95.3	-80.7	93.3	-90.7	98.3	-76.7	89.3	-74.7	87.3	-72.7	91.3	111.3	-152.7	-167.7	136
-166.7	-153.7	119.3	113.3	-100.7	115.3	116.3	-103.7	-104.7	-113.7	-98.7	121.3	122.3	-109.7	124.3	-111.7	126.3	-106.7	167.3	180.3	136
179.3	152.3	144.3	-131.7	146.3	-133.7	148.3	-135.7	150.3	-146.7	168.3	-139.7	154.3	-141.7	156.3	-143.7	158.3	-145.7	-137.7	-165.7	136
187.3	-163.7	176.3	-161.7	174.3	-159.7	172.3	-157.7	170.3	-155.7	-192.7	-184.7	199.3	-186.7	201.3	-188.7	203.3	-190.7	205.3	188.3	136
136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4n}{20} = \frac{4 \times 136}{20} = 27.2 & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12n}{20} = \frac{12 \times 136}{20} = 81.6 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6n}{20} = \frac{6 \times 136}{20} = 40.8 & S_{14 \times 14} &:= \frac{14n}{20} = \frac{14 \times 136}{20} = 95.2 \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8n}{20} = \frac{8 \times 136}{20} = 54.4 & S_{16 \times 16} &:= \frac{16n}{20} = \frac{16 \times 136}{20} = 108.8 \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10n}{20} = \frac{10 \times 134}{20} = 68 & S_{18 \times 18} &:= \frac{18n}{20} = \frac{18 \times 136}{20} = 122.4 \\
 & & S_{20 \times 20} &:= 136.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 5. Let's consider $n = 142$ in (2), we get

-174.4	177.6	-162.4	175.6	-160.4	173.6	-158.4	171.6	-156.4	169.6	206.6	198.6	-185.4	200.6	-187.4	202.6	-189.4	204.6	-191.4	-173.4	142
196.6	151.6	-130.4	145.6	-132.4	147.6	-134.4	149.6	-136.4	160.6	-154.4	153.6	-140.4	155.6	-142.4	157.6	-144.4	159.6	-138.4	-182.4	142
-181.4	142.6	120.6	-99.4	114.6	-101.4	-102.4	117.6	118.6	127.6	112.6	-107.4	-108.4	123.6	-110.4	125.6	-112.4	-105.4	-128.4	195.6	142
194.6	-127.4	133.6	-77.4	-83.4	96.6	-81.4	94.6	-79.4	104.6	-84.4	90.6	-75.4	88.6	-73.4	86.6	92.6	-119.4	141.6	-180.4	142
-179.4	140.6	-118.4	103.6	68.6	77.6	-62.4	75.6	-60.4	-64.4	-43.4	58.6	-45.4	60.6	-47.4	67.6	-89.4	132.6	-126.4	193.6	142
192.6	-125.4	131.6	-88.4	-49.4	47.6	42.6	-27.4	40.6	-25.4	-29.4	-39.4	54.6	-41.4	48.6	63.6	102.6	-117.4	139.6	-178.4	142
-177.4	138.6	-116.4	101.6	-50.4	-30.4	-17.4	-23.4	36.6	38.6	25.6	-12.4	27.6	-18.4	44.6	64.6	-87.4	130.6	-124.4	191.6	142
190.6	-123.4	129.6	-86.4	65.6	45.6	-20.4	20.6	18.6	-8.4	24.6	-7.4	-5.4	34.6	-31.4	-51.4	100.6	-115.4	137.6	-176.4	142
189.6	136.6	-114.4	99.6	66.6	-32.4	-19.4	-9.4	12.6	-0.4	2.6	13.6	23.6	33.6	46.6	-52.4	-85.4	128.6	-122.4	-175.4	142
-164.4	-121.4	-120.4	85.6	73.6	52.6	-14.4	-3.4	5.6	10.6	7.6	4.6	17.6	28.6	-38.4	-59.4	-71.4	134.6	135.6	178.6	142
-183.4	-129.4	-91.4	79.6	62.6	-42.4	35.6	-1.4	9.6	6.6	3.6	8.6	15.6	-21.4	56.6	-48.4	-65.4	105.6	143.6	197.6	142
-172.4	-147.4	106.6	-66.4	-55.4	49.6	30.6	16.6	0.6	11.6	14.6	1.6	-2.4	-16.4	-35.4	69.6	80.6	-92.4	161.6	186.6	142
-171.4	162.6	-93.4	81.6	-56.4	-36.4	29.6	19.6	-4.4	22.6	-10.4	21.6	-6.4	-15.4	50.6	70.6	-67.4	107.6	-148.4	185.6	142
184.6	-149.4	108.6	-68.4	71.6	51.6	32.6	37.6	-22.4	-24.4	-11.4	26.6	-13.4	31.6	-37.4	-57.4	82.6	-94.4	163.6	-170.4	142
183.6	164.6	-95.4	83.6	-58.4	-34.4	-28.4	41.6	-26.4	39.6	43.6	53.6	-40.4	55.6	-33.4	72.6	-69.4	109.6	-150.4	-169.4	142
-168.4	-151.4	110.6	-70.4	-53.4	-63.4	76.6	-61.4	74.6	78.6	57.6	-44.4	59.6	-46.4	61.6	-54.4	84.6	-96.4	165.6	182.6	142
181.6	166.6	-97.4	-78.4	97.6	-82.4	95.6	-80.4	93.6	-90.4	98.6	-76.4	89.6	-74.4	87.6	-72.4	91.6	111.6	-152.4	-167.4	142
-166.4	-153.4	119.6	113.6	-100.4	115.6	116.6	-103.4	-104.4	-113.4	-98.4	121.6	122.6	-109.4	124.6	-111.4	126.6	-106.4	167.6	180.6	142
179.6	152.6	144.6	-131.4	146.6	-133.4	148.6	-135.4	150.6	-146.4	168.6	-139.4	154.6	-141.4	156.6	-143.4	158.6	-145.4	-137.4	-165.4	142
187.6	-163.4	176.6	-161.4	174.6	-159.4	172.6	-157.4	170.6	-155.4	-192.4	-184.4	199.6	-186.4	201.6	-188.4	203.6	-190.4	205.6	188.6	142
142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4n}{20} = \frac{4 \times 142}{20} = 28.8 & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12n}{20} = \frac{12 \times 142}{20} = 85.2 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6n}{20} = \frac{6 \times 142}{20} = 42.6 & S_{14 \times 14} &:= \frac{14n}{20} = \frac{14 \times 142}{20} = 99.4 \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8n}{20} = \frac{8 \times 142}{20} = 56.8 & S_{16 \times 16} &:= \frac{16n}{20} = \frac{16 \times 142}{20} = 113.6 \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10n}{20} = \frac{10 \times 142}{20} = 71 & S_{18 \times 18} &:= \frac{18n}{20} = \frac{18 \times 142}{20} = 127.8 \\
 & & S_{20 \times 20} &:= 142.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 6. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 20 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 399, 400\}$, the magic sum is 4010. Considering $n = 4010$ in (2), we get **positive entries nested magic square** of order

20 given by

19	371	31	369	33	367	35	365	37	363	400	392	8	394	6	396	4	398	2	20	4010	
390	345	63	339	61	341	59	343	57	354	39	347	53	349	51	351	49	353	55	11	4010	
12	336	314	94	308	92	91	311	312	321	306	86	85	317	83	319	81	88	65	389	4010	
388	66	327	116	110	290	112	288	114	298	109	284	118	282	120	280	286	74	335	13	4010	
14	334	75	297	262	271	131	269	133	129	150	252	148	254	146	261	104	326	67	387	4010	
386	68	325	105	144	241	236	166	234	168	164	154	248	152	242	257	296	76	333	15	4010	
16	332	77	295	143	163	176	170	230	232	219	181	221	175	238	258	106	324	69	385	4010	
384	70	323	107	259	239	173	214	212	185	218	186	188	228	162	142	294	78	331	17	4010	
383	330	79	293	260	161	174	184	206	193	196	207	217	227	240	141	108	322	71	18	4010	
29	72	73	279	267	246	179	190	199	204	201	198	211	222	155	134	122	328	329	372	4010	
10	64	102	273	256	151	229	192	203	200	197	202	209	172	250	145	128	299	337	391	4010	
21	46	300	127	138	243	224	210	194	205	208	195	191	177	158	263	274	101	355	380	4010	
22	356	100	275	137	157	223	213	189	216	183	215	187	178	244	264	126	301	45	379	4010	
378	44	302	125	265	245	226	231	171	169	182	220	180	225	156	136	276	99	357	23	4010	
377	358	98	277	135	159	165	235	167	233	237	247	153	249	160	266	124	303	43	24	4010	
25	42	304	123	140	130	270	132	268	272	251	149	253	147	255	139	278	97	359	376	4010	
375	360	96	115	291	111	289	113	287	103	292	117	283	119	281	121	285	305	41	26	4010	
27	40	313	307	93	309	310	90	89	80	95	315	316	84	318	82	320	87	361	374	4010	
373	346	338	62	340	60	342	58	344	47	362	54	348	52	350	50	352	48	56	28	4010	
381	30	370	32	368	34	366	36	364	38	1	9	393	7	395	5	397	3	399	382	4010	
4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010	4010

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4n}{20} = \frac{4 \times 4010}{20} = 802 & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12n}{20} = \frac{12 \times 4010}{20} = 2406 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6n}{20} = \frac{6 \times 4010}{20} = 1203 & S_{14 \times 14} &:= \frac{14n}{20} = \frac{14 \times 4010}{20} = 2807 \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8n}{20} = \frac{8 \times 4010}{20} = 1604 & S_{16 \times 16} &:= \frac{16n}{20} = \frac{16 \times 4010}{20} = 3208 \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10n}{20} = \frac{10 \times 4010}{20} = 2005 & S_{18 \times 18} &:= \frac{18n}{20} = \frac{18 \times 4010}{20} = 3609 \\
 & & S_{20 \times 20} &:= 4010.
 \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Nested Magic Square of Order 19

Add each term of magic square of order 19 given in Example (1) by $n/19$, where $n \in Z$ (integer). This gives

Result 2. *Nested magic square of order 19 with symmetric entries and magic sum n , $n \in Z$ (integer) is given by*

-161+n/19	-145+n/19	-147+n/19	-149+n/19	-151+n/19	-153+n/19	-155+n/19	-157+n/19	-159+n/19	164+n/19	165+n/19	167+n/19	169+n/19	171+n/19	173+n/19	175+n/19	177+n/19	179+n/19	-163+n/19	n
180+n/19	-129+n/19	143+n/19	141+n/19	139+n/19	137+n/19	135+n/19	133+n/19	131+n/19	130+n/19	-125+n/19	-123+n/19	-121+n/19	-119+n/19	-117+n/19	-115+n/19	-113+n/19	-127+n/19	-180+n/19	n
178+n/19	-144+n/19	97+n/19	86+n/19	88+n/19	90+n/19	92+n/19	94+n/19	96+n/19	98+n/19	-102+n/19	-104+n/19	-106+n/19	-108+n/19	-110+n/19	-112+n/19	-99+n/19	144+n/19	-178+n/19	n
176+n/19	-142+n/19	-111+n/19	71+n/19	62+n/19	64+n/19	66+n/19	68+n/19	70+n/19	72+n/19	-76+n/19	-78+n/19	-80+n/19	-82+n/19	-84+n/19	-73+n/19	111+n/19	142+n/19	-176+n/19	n
174+n/19	-140+n/19	-109+n/19	-83+n/19	-49+n/19	-41+n/19	-43+n/19	-45+n/19	-47+n/19	52+n/19	53+n/19	55+n/19	57+n/19	59+n/19	-51+n/19	83+n/19	109+n/19	140+n/19	-174+n/19	n
172+n/19	-138+n/19	-107+n/19	-81+n/19	60+n/19	-33+n/19	39+n/19	37+n/19	35+n/19	34+n/19	-29+n/19	-27+n/19	-25+n/19	-31+n/19	-60+n/19	81+n/19	107+n/19	138+n/19	-172+n/19	n
170+n/19	-136+n/19	-105+n/19	-79+n/19	58+n/19	-40+n/19	-17+n/19	-13+n/19	-15+n/19	20+n/19	21+n/19	23+n/19	-19+n/19	40+n/19	-58+n/19	79+n/19	105+n/19	136+n/19	-170+n/19	n
168+n/19	-134+n/19	-103+n/19	-77+n/19	56+n/19	-38+n/19	24+n/19	-9+n/19	-12+n/19	8+n/19	6+n/19	7+n/19	-24+n/19	38+n/19	-56+n/19	77+n/19	103+n/19	134+n/19	-168+n/19	n
166+n/19	-132+n/19	-101+n/19	-75+n/19	54+n/19	-36+n/19	22+n/19	11+n/19	1+n/19	-4+n/19	3+n/19	-11+n/19	-22+n/19	36+n/19	-54+n/19	75+n/19	101+n/19	132+n/19	-166+n/19	n
-16+n/19	128+n/19	-100+n/19	-74+n/19	-50+n/19	32+n/19	-18+n/19	10+n/19	2+n/19	0+n/19	-2+n/19	-10+n/19	18+n/19	-32+n/19	50+n/19	74+n/19	100+n/19	-128+n/19	162+n/19	n
-160+n/19	126+n/19	95+n/19	69+n/19	-48+n/19	30+n/19	-16+n/19	-5+n/19	-3+n/19	4+n/19	-1+n/19	5+n/19	16+n/19	-30+n/19	48+n/19	-69+n/19	-95+n/19	-126+n/19	160+n/19	n
-158+n/19	124+n/19	93+n/19	67+n/19	-46+n/19	28+n/19	-14+n/19	-7+n/19	12+n/19	-8+n/19	-6+n/19	9+n/19	14+n/19	-28+n/19	46+n/19	-67+n/19	-93+n/19	-124+n/19	158+n/19	n
-156+n/19	122+n/19	91+n/19	65+n/19	-44+n/19	26+n/19	19+n/19	13+n/19	15+n/19	-20+n/19	-21+n/19	-23+n/19	17+n/19	-26+n/19	44+n/19	-65+n/19	-91+n/19	-122+n/19	156+n/19	n
-154+n/19	120+n/19	89+n/19	63+n/19	-42+n/19	31+n/19	-39+n/19	-37+n/19	-35+n/19	-34+n/19	29+n/19	27+n/19	25+n/19	33+n/19	42+n/19	-63+n/19	-89+n/19	-120+n/19	154+n/19	n
-152+n/19	118+n/19	87+n/19	61+n/19	51+n/19	41+n/19	43+n/19	45+n/19	47+n/19	-52+n/19	-53+n/19	-55+n/19	-57+n/19	-59+n/19	49+n/19	-61+n/19	-87+n/19	-118+n/19	152+n/19	n
-150+n/19	116+n/19	85+n/19	73+n/19	-62+n/19	-64+n/19	-66+n/19	-68+n/19	-70+n/19	-72+n/19	76+n/19	78+n/19	80+n/19	82+n/19	84+n/19	-71+n/19	-85+n/19	-116+n/19	150+n/19	n
-148+n/19	114+n/19	99+n/19	-86+n/19	-88+n/19	-90+n/19	-92+n/19	-94+n/19	-96+n/19	-98+n/19	102+n/19	104+n/19	106+n/19	108+n/19	110+n/19	112+n/19	-97+n/19	-114+n/19	148+n/19	n
-146+n/19	127+n/19	-143+n/19	-141+n/19	-139+n/19	-137+n/19	-135+n/19	-133+n/19	-131+n/19	-130+n/19	125+n/19	123+n/19	121+n/19	119+n/19	117+n/19	115+n/19	113+n/19	129+n/19	146+n/19	n
163+n/19	145+n/19	147+n/19	149+n/19	151+n/19	153+n/19	155+n/19	157+n/19	159+n/19	-164+n/19	-165+n/19	-167+n/19	-169+n/19	-171+n/19	-173+n/19	-175+n/19	-177+n/19	-179+n/19	161+n/19	n
n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n

(3)

In this case, the magic sums are given by,

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{19}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{19}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{19}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{19}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{19}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13n}{19}$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{15n}{19}$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{17n}{19}$$

$$S_{19 \times 19} := n.$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm 179, \pm 180\}$.

Example 7. Let's consider $n = 139$ in (3), we get

-153 13/19	-137 13/19	-139 13/19	-141 13/19	-143 13/19	-145 13/19	-147 13/19	-149 13/19	-151 13/19	171 6/19	172 6/19	174 6/19	176 6/19	178 6/19	180 6/19	182 6/19	184 6/19	186 6/19	-155 13/19	139
187 6/19	-121 13/19	150 6/19	148 6/19	146 6/19	144 6/19	142 6/19	140 6/19	138 6/19	137 6/19	-117 13/19	-115 13/19	-113 13/19	-111 13/19	-109 13/19	-107 13/19	-105 13/19	-119 13/19	-172 13/19	139
185 6/19	-136 13/19	104 6/19	93 6/19	95 6/19	97 6/19	99 6/19	101 6/19	103 6/19	105 6/19	-94 13/19	-96 13/19	-98 13/19	-100 13/19	-102 13/19	-104 13/19	-91 13/19	151 6/19	-170 13/19	139
183 6/19	-134 13/19	-103 13/19	78 6/19	69 6/19	71 6/19	73 6/19	75 6/19	77 6/19	79 6/19	-68 13/19	-70 13/19	-72 13/19	-74 13/19	-76 13/19	-65 13/19	118 6/19	149 6/19	-168 13/19	139
181 6/19	-132 13/19	-101 13/19	-75 13/19	-41 13/19	-33 13/19	-35 13/19	-37 13/19	-39 13/19	59 6/19	60 6/19	62 6/19	64 6/19	66 6/19	-43 13/19	90 6/19	116 6/19	147 6/19	-166 13/19	139
179 6/19	-130 13/19	-99 13/19	-73 13/19	67 6/19	-25 13/19	46 6/19	44 6/19	42 6/19	41 6/19	-21 13/19	-19 13/19	-17 13/19	-23 13/19	-52 13/19	88 6/19	114 6/19	145 6/19	-164 13/19	139
177 6/19	-128 13/19	-97 13/19	-71 13/19	65 6/19	-32 13/19	-9 13/19	-5 13/19	-7 13/19	27 6/19	28 6/19	30 6/19	-11 13/19	47 6/19	-50 13/19	86 6/19	112 6/19	143 6/19	-162 13/19	139
175 6/19	-126 13/19	-95 13/19	-69 13/19	63 6/19	-30 13/19	31 6/19	-1 13/19	-4 13/19	15 6/19	13 6/19	14 6/19	-16 13/19	45 6/19	-48 13/19	84 6/19	110 6/19	141 6/19	-160 13/19	139
173 6/19	-124 13/19	-93 13/19	-67 13/19	61 6/19	-28 13/19	29 6/19	18 6/19	8 6/19	3 6/19	10 6/19	-3 13/19	-14 13/19	43 6/19	-46 13/19	82 6/19	108 6/19	139 6/19	-158 13/19	139
-154 13/19	135 6/19	-92 13/19	-66 13/19	-42 13/19	39 6/19	-10 13/19	17 6/19	9 6/19	7 6/19	5 6/19	-2 13/19	25 6/19	-24 13/19	57 6/19	81 6/19	107 6/19	-120 13/19	169 6/19	139
-152 13/19	133 6/19	102 6/19	76 6/19	-40 13/19	37 6/19	-8 13/19	2 6/19	4 6/19	11 6/19	6 6/19	12 6/19	23 6/19	-22 13/19	55 6/19	-61 13/19	-87 13/19	-118 13/19	167 6/19	139
-150 13/19	131 6/19	100 6/19	74 6/19	-38 13/19	35 6/19	-6 13/19	6/19	19 6/19	-13/19	1 6/19	16 6/19	21 6/19	-20 13/19	53 6/19	-59 13/19	-85 13/19	-116 13/19	165 6/19	139
-148 13/19	129 6/19	98 6/19	72 6/19	-36 13/19	33 6/19	26 6/19	20 6/19	22 6/19	-12 13/19	-13 13/19	-15 13/19	24 6/19	-18 13/19	51 6/19	-57 13/19	-83 13/19	-114 13/19	163 6/19	139
-146 13/19	127 6/19	96 6/19	70 6/19	-34 13/19	38 6/19	-31 13/19	-29 13/19	-27 13/19	-26 13/19	36 6/19	34 6/19	32 6/19	40 6/19	49 6/19	-55 13/19	-81 13/19	-112 13/19	161 6/19	139
-144 13/19	125 6/19	94 6/19	68 6/19	58 6/19	48 6/19	50 6/19	52 6/19	54 6/19	-44 13/19	-45 13/19	-47 13/19	-49 13/19	-51 13/19	56 6/19	-53 13/19	-79 13/19	-110 13/19	159 6/19	139
-142 13/19	123 6/19	92 6/19	80 6/19	-54 13/19	-56 13/19	-58 13/19	-60 13/19	-62 13/19	-64 13/19	83 6/19	85 6/19	87 6/19	89 6/19	91 6/19	-63 13/19	-77 13/19	-108 13/19	157 6/19	139
-140 13/19	121 6/19	106 6/19	-78 13/19	-80 13/19	-82 13/19	-84 13/19	-86 13/19	-88 13/19	-90 13/19	109 6/19	111 6/19	113 6/19	115 6/19	117 6/19	119 6/19	-89 13/19	-106 13/19	155 6/19	139
-138 13/19	134 6/19	-135 13/19	-133 13/19	-131 13/19	-129 13/19	-127 13/19	-125 13/19	-123 13/19	-122 13/19	132 6/19	130 6/19	128 6/19	126 6/19	124 6/19	122 6/19	120 6/19	136 6/19	153 6/19	139
170 6/19	152 6/19	154 6/19	156 6/19	158 6/19	160 6/19	162 6/19	164 6/19	166 6/19	-156 13/19	-157 13/19	-159 13/19	-161 13/19	-163 13/19	-165 13/19	-167 13/19	-169 13/19	-171 13/19	168 6/19	139
139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139	139

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{19} = \frac{3 \times 139}{19} = \frac{417}{19}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{19} = \frac{5 \times 139}{19} = \frac{695}{19}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{19} = \frac{7 \times 139}{19} = \frac{973}{19}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{19} = \frac{9 \times 139}{19} = \frac{1251}{19}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{19} = \frac{11 \times 139}{19} = \frac{1529}{19}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13n}{19} = \frac{13 \times 139}{19} = \frac{1807}{19}$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{15n}{19} = \frac{15 \times 139}{19} = \frac{2085}{19}$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{17n}{19} = \frac{17 \times 139}{19} = \frac{2363}{19}$$

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 138.$$

Example 8. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 19 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 360, 361\}$, the magic sum is 3439. Considering $n = 3439$ in (3), we get **positive entries nested magic square** of order 19 given by

																			3439
20	36	34	32	30	28	26	24	22	345	346	348	350	352	354	356	358	360	18	3439
361	52	324	322	320	318	316	314	312	311	56	58	60	62	64	66	68	54	1	3439
359	37	278	267	269	271	273	275	277	279	79	77	75	73	71	69	82	325	3	3439
357	39	70	252	243	245	247	249	251	253	105	103	101	99	97	108	292	323	5	3439
355	41	72	98	132	140	138	136	134	233	234	236	238	240	130	264	290	321	7	3439
353	43	74	100	241	148	220	218	216	215	152	154	156	150	121	262	288	319	9	3439
351	45	76	102	239	141	164	168	166	201	202	204	162	221	123	260	286	317	11	3439
349	47	78	104	237	143	205	172	169	189	187	188	157	219	125	258	284	315	13	3439
347	49	80	106	235	145	203	192	182	177	184	170	159	217	127	256	282	313	15	3439
19	309	81	107	131	213	163	191	183	181	179	171	199	149	231	255	281	53	343	3439
21	307	276	250	133	211	165	176	178	185	180	186	197	151	229	112	86	55	341	3439
23	305	274	248	135	209	167	174	193	173	175	190	195	153	227	114	88	57	339	3439
25	303	272	246	137	207	200	194	196	161	160	158	198	155	225	116	90	59	337	3439
27	301	270	244	139	212	142	144	146	147	210	208	206	214	223	118	92	61	335	3439
29	299	268	242	232	222	224	226	228	129	128	126	124	122	230	120	94	63	333	3439
31	297	266	254	119	117	115	113	111	109	257	259	261	263	265	110	96	65	331	3439
33	295	280	95	93	91	89	87	85	83	283	285	287	289	291	293	84	67	329	3439
35	308	38	40	42	44	46	48	50	51	306	304	302	300	298	296	294	310	327	3439
344	326	328	330	332	334	336	338	340	17	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	342	3439
3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439	3439

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{19} = \frac{3 \times 2465}{19} = 543$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{19} = \frac{5 \times 2465}{19} = 905$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{19} = \frac{7 \times 2465}{19} = 1267$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{19} = \frac{9 \times 2465}{19} = 1629$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{19} = \frac{11 \times 2465}{19} = 1991$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13n}{19} = \frac{13 \times 2465}{19} = 2353$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{15n}{19} = \frac{15 \times 2465}{19} = 2715$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := \frac{15n}{19} = \frac{15 \times 2465}{19} = 3077$$

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 3439.$$

2.3 Nested Magic Square of Order 18

Result 3. *Nested magic square of order 18 with symmetric entries and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by*

144.5+n/18	-137.5+n/18	138.5+n/18	-139.5+n/18	140.5+n/18	-141.5+n/18	142.5+n/18	-143.5+n/18	153.5+n/18	-161.5+n/18	146.5+n/18	-147.5+n/18	148.5+n/18	-149.5+n/18	150.5+n/18	-151.5+n/18	152.5+n/18	-145.5+n/18
135.5+n/18	113.5+n/18	-106.5+n/18	107.5+n/18	-108.5+n/18	-109.5+n/18	110.5+n/18	111.5+n/18	120.5+n/18	105.5+n/18	-114.5+n/18	-115.5+n/18	116.5+n/18	-117.5+n/18	118.5+n/18	-119.5+n/18	-112.5+n/18	-135.5+n/18
-134.5+n/18	126.5+n/18	-84.5+n/18	-90.5+n/18	89.5+n/18	-88.5+n/18	87.5+n/18	-86.5+n/18	97.5+n/18	-91.5+n/18	83.5+n/18	-82.5+n/18	81.5+n/18	-80.5+n/18	79.5+n/18	85.5+n/18	-126.5+n/18	134.5+n/18
133.5+n/18	-125.5+n/18	96.5+n/18	61.5+n/18	70.5+n/18	-69.5+n/18	68.5+n/18	-67.5+n/18	-71.5+n/18	-50.5+n/18	51.5+n/18	-52.5+n/18	53.5+n/18	-54.5+n/18	60.5+n/18	-96.5+n/18	125.5+n/18	-133.5+n/18
-132.5+n/18	124.5+n/18	-95.5+n/18	-56.5+n/18	40.5+n/18	35.5+n/18	-34.5+n/18	33.5+n/18	-32.5+n/18	-36.5+n/18	-46.5+n/18	47.5+n/18	-48.5+n/18	41.5+n/18	56.5+n/18	95.5+n/18	-124.5+n/18	132.5+n/18
131.5+n/18	-123.5+n/18	94.5+n/18	-57.5+n/18	-37.5+n/18	-24.5+n/18	-30.5+n/18	29.5+n/18	31.5+n/18	18.5+n/18	-19.5+n/18	20.5+n/18	-25.5+n/18	37.5+n/18	57.5+n/18	-94.5+n/18	123.5+n/18	-131.5+n/18
-130.5+n/18	122.5+n/18	-93.5+n/18	58.5+n/18	38.5+n/18	-27.5+n/18	13.5+n/18	11.5+n/18	-15.5+n/18	17.5+n/18	-14.5+n/18	-12.5+n/18	27.5+n/18	-38.5+n/18	-58.5+n/18	93.5+n/18	-122.5+n/18	130.5+n/18
129.5+n/18	-121.5+n/18	92.5+n/18	59.5+n/18	-39.5+n/18	-26.5+n/18	-16.5+n/18	5.5+n/18	-7.5+n/18	-4.5+n/18	6.5+n/18	16.5+n/18	26.5+n/18	39.5+n/18	-59.5+n/18	-92.5+n/18	121.5+n/18	-129.5+n/18
-128.5+n/18	-127.5+n/18	78.5+n/18	66.5+n/18	45.5+n/18	-21.5+n/18	-10.5+n/18	-1.5+n/18	3.5+n/18	0.5+n/18	-2.5+n/18	10.5+n/18	21.5+n/18	-45.5+n/18	-66.5+n/18	-78.5+n/18	127.5+n/18	128.5+n/18
-136.5+n/18	-98.5+n/18	72.5+n/18	55.5+n/18	-49.5+n/18	28.5+n/18	-8.5+n/18	2.5+n/18	-0.5+n/18	-3.5+n/18	1.5+n/18	8.5+n/18	-28.5+n/18	49.5+n/18	-55.5+n/18	-72.5+n/18	98.5+n/18	136.5+n/18
-154.5+n/18	99.5+n/18	-73.5+n/18	-62.5+n/18	42.5+n/18	23.5+n/18	9.5+n/18	-6.5+n/18	4.5+n/18	7.5+n/18	-5.5+n/18	-9.5+n/18	-23.5+n/18	-42.5+n/18	62.5+n/18	73.5+n/18	-99.5+n/18	154.5+n/18
155.5+n/18	-100.5+n/18	74.5+n/18	-63.5+n/18	-43.5+n/18	22.5+n/18	12.5+n/18	-11.5+n/18	15.5+n/18	-17.5+n/18	14.5+n/18	-13.5+n/18	-22.5+n/18	43.5+n/18	63.5+n/18	-74.5+n/18	100.5+n/18	-155.5+n/18
-156.5+n/18	101.5+n/18	-75.5+n/18	64.5+n/18	44.5+n/18	25.5+n/18	30.5+n/18	-29.5+n/18	-31.5+n/18	-18.5+n/18	19.5+n/18	-20.5+n/18	24.5+n/18	-44.5+n/18	-64.5+n/18	75.5+n/18	-101.5+n/18	156.5+n/18
157.5+n/18	-102.5+n/18	76.5+n/18	-65.5+n/18	-41.5+n/18	-35.5+n/18	34.5+n/18	-33.5+n/18	32.5+n/18	36.5+n/18	46.5+n/18	-47.5+n/18	48.5+n/18	-40.5+n/18	65.5+n/18	-76.5+n/18	102.5+n/18	-157.5+n/18
-158.5+n/18	103.5+n/18	-77.5+n/18	-60.5+n/18	-70.5+n/18	69.5+n/18	-68.5+n/18	67.5+n/18	71.5+n/18	50.5+n/18	-51.5+n/18	52.5+n/18	-53.5+n/18	54.5+n/18	-61.5+n/18	77.5+n/18	-103.5+n/18	158.5+n/18
159.5+n/18	-104.5+n/18	-85.5+n/18	90.5+n/18	-89.5+n/18	88.5+n/18	-87.5+n/18	86.5+n/18	-97.5+n/18	91.5+n/18	-83.5+n/18	82.5+n/18	-81.5+n/18	80.5+n/18	-79.5+n/18	84.5+n/18	104.5+n/18	-159.5+n/18
-160.5+n/18	112.5+n/18	106.5+n/18	-107.5+n/18	108.5+n/18	109.5+n/18	-110.5+n/18	-111.5+n/18	-120.5+n/18	-105.5+n/18	114.5+n/18	115.5+n/18	-116.5+n/18	117.5+n/18	-118.5+n/18	119.5+n/18	-113.5+n/18	160.5+n/18
145.5+n/18	137.5+n/18	-138.5+n/18	139.5+n/18	-140.5+n/18	141.5+n/18	-142.5+n/18	143.5+n/18	-153.5+n/18	161.5+n/18	-146.5+n/18	147.5+n/18	-148.5+n/18	149.5+n/18	-150.5+n/18	151.5+n/18	-152.5+n/18	-144.5+n/18
n																	

(4)

In this case, the magic sums are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4n}{18} = \frac{2n}{9} & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12n}{18} = \frac{2n}{3} \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6n}{18} = \frac{n}{3} & S_{14 \times 14} &:= \frac{14n}{18} = \frac{7n}{9} \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8n}{18} = \frac{4n}{9} & S_{16 \times 16} &:= \frac{16n}{18} = \frac{8n}{9} \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10n}{18} = \frac{5n}{9} & S_{18 \times 18} &:= \frac{18n}{18} = n.
 \end{aligned}$$

For $n = 0$, the *symmetric entries* are $\{\pm 0.5, \pm 1.5, \dots, \pm 160.5 \pm 161.5\}$.

Example 9. Let's consider $n = 133$ in (4), we get

151 8/9	-130 1/9	145 8/9	-132 1/9	147 8/9	-134 1/9	149 8/9	-136 1/9	160 8/9	-154 1/9	153 8/9	-140 1/9	155 8/9	-142 1/9	157 8/9	-144 1/9	159 8/9	-138 1/9	133
142 8/9	120 8/9	-99 1/9	114 8/9	-101 1/9	-102 1/9	117 8/9	118 8/9	127 8/9	112 8/9	-107 1/9	-108 1/9	123 8/9	-110 1/9	125 8/9	-112 1/9	-105 1/9	-128 1/9	133
-127 1/9	133 8/9	-77 1/9	-83 1/9	96 8/9	-81 1/9	94 8/9	-79 1/9	104 8/9	-84 1/9	90 8/9	-75 1/9	88 8/9	-73 1/9	86 8/9	92 8/9	-119 1/9	141 8/9	133
140 8/9	-118 1/9	103 8/9	68 8/9	77 8/9	-62 1/9	75 8/9	-60 1/9	-64 1/9	-43 1/9	58 8/9	-45 1/9	60 8/9	-47 1/9	67 8/9	-89 1/9	132 8/9	-126 1/9	133
-125 1/9	131 8/9	-88 1/9	-49 1/9	47 8/9	42 8/9	-27 1/9	40 8/9	-25 1/9	-29 1/9	-39 1/9	54 8/9	-41 1/9	48 8/9	63 8/9	102 8/9	-117 1/9	139 8/9	133
138 8/9	-116 1/9	101 8/9	-50 1/9	-30 1/9	-17 1/9	-23 1/9	36 8/9	38 8/9	25 8/9	-12 1/9	27 8/9	-18 1/9	44 8/9	64 8/9	-87 1/9	130 8/9	-124 1/9	133
-123 1/9	129 8/9	-86 1/9	65 8/9	45 8/9	-20 1/9	20 8/9	18 8/9	-8 1/9	24 8/9	-7 1/9	-5 1/9	34 8/9	-31 1/9	-51 1/9	100 8/9	-115 1/9	137 8/9	133
136 8/9	-114 1/9	99 8/9	66 8/9	-32 1/9	-19 1/9	-9 1/9	12 8/9	-1 1/9	2 8/9	13 8/9	23 8/9	33 8/9	46 8/9	-52 1/9	-85 1/9	128 8/9	-122 1/9	133
-121 1/9	-120 1/9	85 8/9	73 8/9	52 8/9	-14 1/9	-3 1/9	5 8/9	10 8/9	7 8/9	4 8/9	17 8/9	28 8/9	-38 1/9	-59 1/9	-71 1/9	134 8/9	135 8/9	133
-129 1/9	-91 1/9	79 8/9	62 8/9	-42 1/9	35 8/9	-11 1/9	9 8/9	6 8/9	3 8/9	8 8/9	15 8/9	-21 1/9	56 8/9	-48 1/9	-65 1/9	105 8/9	143 8/9	133
-147 1/9	106 8/9	-66 1/9	-55 1/9	49 8/9	30 8/9	16 8/9	8 1/9	11 8/9	14 8/9	18 1/9	-2 1/9	-16 1/9	-35 1/9	69 8/9	80 8/9	-92 1/9	161 8/9	133
162 8/9	-93 1/9	81 8/9	-56 1/9	-36 1/9	29 8/9	19 8/9	-4 1/9	22 8/9	-10 1/9	21 8/9	-6 1/9	-15 1/9	50 8/9	70 8/9	-67 1/9	107 8/9	-148 1/9	133
-149 1/9	108 8/9	-68 1/9	71 8/9	51 8/9	32 8/9	37 8/9	-22 1/9	-24 1/9	-11 1/9	26 8/9	-13 1/9	31 8/9	-37 1/9	-57 1/9	82 8/9	-94 1/9	163 8/9	133
164 8/9	-95 1/9	83 8/9	-58 1/9	-34 1/9	-28 1/9	41 8/9	-26 1/9	39 8/9	43 8/9	53 8/9	-40 1/9	55 8/9	-33 1/9	72 8/9	-69 1/9	109 8/9	-150 1/9	133
-151 1/9	110 8/9	-70 1/9	-53 1/9	-63 1/9	76 8/9	-61 1/9	74 8/9	78 8/9	57 8/9	-44 1/9	59 8/9	-46 1/9	61 8/9	-54 1/9	84 8/9	-96 1/9	165 8/9	133
166 8/9	-97 1/9	-78 1/9	97 8/9	-82 1/9	95 8/9	-80 1/9	93 8/9	-90 1/9	98 8/9	-76 1/9	89 8/9	-74 1/9	87 8/9	-72 1/9	91 8/9	111 8/9	-152 1/9	133
-153 1/9	119 8/9	113 8/9	-100 1/9	115 8/9	116 8/9	-103 1/9	-104 1/9	-113 1/9	-98 1/9	121 8/9	122 8/9	-109 1/9	124 8/9	-111 1/9	126 8/9	-106 1/9	167 8/9	133
152 8/9	144 8/9	-131 1/9	146 8/9	-133 1/9	148 8/9	-135 1/9	150 8/9	-146 1/9	168 8/9	-139 1/9	154 8/9	-141 1/9	156 8/9	-143 1/9	158 8/9	-145 1/9	-137 1/9	133
133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4n}{18} = \frac{4 \times 133}{18} = \frac{266}{9} & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12n}{18} = \frac{12 \times 133}{18} = \frac{266}{3} \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6n}{18} = \frac{6 \times 133}{18} = \frac{133}{3} & S_{14 \times 14} &:= \frac{14n}{18} = \frac{14 \times 133}{18} = \frac{931}{9} \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8n}{18} = \frac{8 \times 133}{18} = \frac{532}{9} & S_{16 \times 16} &:= \frac{16n}{18} = \frac{16 \times 133}{18} = \frac{1064}{9} \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10n}{18} = \frac{10 \times 133}{18} = \frac{665}{9} & S_{18 \times 18} &:= 133.
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 10. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 18 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 323, 324\}$, the magic sum is 2925. Considering $n = 2925$ in (4), we get *positive entries nested magic square* of order 18 given by

307	25	301	23	303	21	305	19	316	1	309	15	311	13	313	11	315	17	2925	
298	276	56	270	54	53	273	274	283	268	48	47	279	45	281	43	50	27	2925	
28	289	78	72	252	74	250	76	260	71	246	80	244	82	242	248	36	297	2925	
296	37	259	224	233	93	231	95	91	112	214	110	216	108	223	66	288	29	2925	
30	287	67	106	203	198	128	196	130	126	116	210	114	204	219	258	38	295	2925	
294	39	257	105	125	138	132	192	194	181	143	183	137	200	220	68	286	31	2925	
32	285	69	221	201	135	176	174	147	180	148	150	190	124	104	256	40	293	2925	
292	41	255	222	123	136	146	168	155	158	169	179	189	202	103	70	284	33	2925	
34	35	241	229	208	141	152	161	166	163	160	173	184	117	96	84	290	291	2925	
26	64	235	218	113	191	154	165	162	159	164	171	134	212	107	90	261	299	2925	
8	262	89	100	205	186	172	156	167	170	157	153	139	120	225	236	63	317	2925	
318	62	237	99	119	185	175	151	178	145	177	149	140	206	226	88	263	7	2925	
6	264	87	227	207	188	193	133	131	144	182	142	187	118	98	238	61	319	2925	
320	60	239	97	121	127	197	129	195	199	209	115	211	122	228	86	265	5	2925	
4	266	85	102	92	232	94	230	234	213	111	215	109	217	101	240	59	321	2925	
322	58	77	253	73	251	75	249	65	254	79	245	81	243	83	247	267	3	2925	
2	275	269	55	271	272	52	51	42	57	277	278	46	280	44	282	49	323	2925	
308	300	24	302	22	304	20	306	9	324	16	310	14	312	12	314	10	18	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4n}{18} = \frac{4 \times 2925}{18} = 650 & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12n}{18} = \frac{12 \times 2925}{18} = 1950 \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6n}{18} = \frac{6 \times 2925}{18} = 975 & S_{14 \times 14} &:= \frac{14n}{18} = \frac{14 \times 2925}{18} = 2275 \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8n}{18} = \frac{8 \times 2925}{18} = 1300 & S_{16 \times 16} &:= \frac{16n}{18} = \frac{16 \times 2925}{18} = 1600 \\
 S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10n}{18} = \frac{10 \times 2925}{18} = 1625 & S_{18 \times 18} &:= 2925.
 \end{aligned}$$

2.4 Nested Magic Square of Order 17

Result 4. *Nested magic square of order 17 with symmetric entries and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by*

-129+n/17	143+n/17	141+n/17	139+n/17	137+n/17	135+n/17	133+n/17	131+n/17	130+n/17	-125+n/17	-123+n/17	-121+n/17	-119+n/17	-117+n/17	-115+n/17	-113+n/17	-127+n/17	n
-144+n/17	97+n/17	86+n/17	88+n/17	90+n/17	92+n/17	94+n/17	96+n/17	98+n/17	-102+n/17	-104+n/17	-106+n/17	-108+n/17	-110+n/17	-112+n/17	-99+n/17	144+n/17	n
-142+n/17	-111+n/17	71+n/17	62+n/17	64+n/17	66+n/17	68+n/17	70+n/17	72+n/17	-76+n/17	-78+n/17	-80+n/17	-82+n/17	-84+n/17	-73+n/17	111+n/17	142+n/17	n
-140+n/17	-109+n/17	-83+n/17	-49+n/17	-41+n/17	-43+n/17	-45+n/17	-47+n/17	52+n/17	53+n/17	55+n/17	57+n/17	59+n/17	-51+n/17	83+n/17	109+n/17	140+n/17	n
-138+n/17	-107+n/17	-81+n/17	60+n/17	-33+n/17	39+n/17	37+n/17	35+n/17	34+n/17	-29+n/17	-27+n/17	-25+n/17	-31+n/17	-60+n/17	81+n/17	107+n/17	138+n/17	n
-136+n/17	-105+n/17	-79+n/17	58+n/17	-40+n/17	-17+n/17	-13+n/17	-15+n/17	20+n/17	21+n/17	23+n/17	-19+n/17	40+n/17	-58+n/17	79+n/17	105+n/17	136+n/17	n
-134+n/17	-103+n/17	-77+n/17	56+n/17	-38+n/17	24+n/17	-9+n/17	-12+n/17	8+n/17	6+n/17	7+n/17	-24+n/17	38+n/17	-56+n/17	77+n/17	103+n/17	134+n/17	n
-132+n/17	-101+n/17	-75+n/17	54+n/17	-36+n/17	22+n/17	11+n/17	1+n/17	-4+n/17	3+n/17	-11+n/17	-22+n/17	36+n/17	-54+n/17	75+n/17	101+n/17	132+n/17	n
128+n/17	-100+n/17	-74+n/17	-50+n/17	32+n/17	-18+n/17	10+n/17	2+n/17	0+n/17	-2+n/17	-10+n/17	18+n/17	-32+n/17	50+n/17	74+n/17	100+n/17	-128+n/17	n
126+n/17	95+n/17	69+n/17	-48+n/17	30+n/17	-16+n/17	-5+n/17	-3+n/17	4+n/17	-1+n/17	5+n/17	16+n/17	-30+n/17	48+n/17	-69+n/17	-95+n/17	-126+n/17	n
124+n/17	93+n/17	67+n/17	-46+n/17	28+n/17	-14+n/17	-7+n/17	12+n/17	-8+n/17	-6+n/17	9+n/17	14+n/17	-28+n/17	46+n/17	-67+n/17	-93+n/17	-124+n/17	n
122+n/17	91+n/17	65+n/17	-44+n/17	26+n/17	19+n/17	13+n/17	15+n/17	-20+n/17	-21+n/17	-23+n/17	17+n/17	-26+n/17	44+n/17	-65+n/17	-91+n/17	-122+n/17	n
120+n/17	89+n/17	63+n/17	-42+n/17	31+n/17	-39+n/17	-37+n/17	-35+n/17	-34+n/17	29+n/17	27+n/17	25+n/17	33+n/17	42+n/17	-63+n/17	-89+n/17	-120+n/17	n
118+n/17	87+n/17	61+n/17	51+n/17	41+n/17	43+n/17	45+n/17	47+n/17	-52+n/17	-53+n/17	-55+n/17	-57+n/17	-59+n/17	49+n/17	-61+n/17	-87+n/17	-118+n/17	n
116+n/17	85+n/17	73+n/17	-62	-64+n/17	-66+n/17	-68+n/17	-70+n/17	-72+n/17	76+n/17	78+n/17	80+n/17	82+n/17	84+n/17	-71+n/17	-85+n/17	-116+n/17	n
114+n/17	99+n/17	-86+n/17	-88	-90+n/17	-92+n/17	-94+n/17	-96+n/17	-98+n/17	102+n/17	104+n/17	106+n/17	108+n/17	110+n/17	112+n/17	-97+n/17	-114+n/17	n
127+n/17	-143+n/17	-141+n/17	-139+n/17	-137+n/17	-135+n/17	-133+n/17	-131+n/17	-130+n/17	125+n/17	123+n/17	121+n/17	119+n/17	117+n/17	115+n/17	113+n/17	129+n/17	n
n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n

(5)

In this case, the magic sums are given by,

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{17}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{17}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{17}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{17}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{17}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13n}{17}$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{15n}{17}$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := n.$$

For $n = 0$, the *symmetric entries* are $\{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm 143, \pm 144\}$.

Example 11. Let's consider $n = 138$ in (5), we get

-120 15/17	151 2/17	149 2/17	147 2/17	145 2/17	143 2/17	141 2/17	139 2/17	138 2/17	-116 15/17	-114 15/17	-112 15/17	-110 15/17	-108 15/17	-106 15/17	-104 15/17	-118 15/17	138
-135 15/17	105 2/17	94 2/17	96 2/17	98 2/17	100 2/17	102 2/17	104 2/17	106 2/17	-93 15/17	-95 15/17	-97 15/17	-99 15/17	-101 15/17	-103 15/17	-90 15/17	152 2/17	138
-133 15/17	-102 15/17	79 2/17	70 2/17	72 2/17	74 2/17	76 2/17	78 2/17	80 2/17	-67 15/17	-69 15/17	-71 15/17	-73 15/17	-75 15/17	-64 15/17	119 2/17	150 2/17	138
-131 15/17	-100 15/17	-74 15/17	-40 15/17	-32 15/17	-34 15/17	-36 15/17	-38 15/17	60 2/17	61 2/17	63 2/17	65 2/17	67 2/17	-42 15/17	91 2/17	117 2/17	148 2/17	138
-129 15/17	-98 15/17	-72 15/17	68 2/17	-24 15/17	47 2/17	45 2/17	43 2/17	42 2/17	-20 15/17	-18 15/17	-16 15/17	-22 15/17	-51 15/17	89 2/17	115 2/17	146 2/17	138
-127 15/17	-96 15/17	-70 15/17	66 2/17	-31 15/17	-8 15/17	-4 15/17	-6 15/17	28 2/17	29 2/17	31 2/17	-10 15/17	48 2/17	-49 15/17	87 2/17	113 2/17	144 2/17	138
-125 15/17	-94 15/17	-68 15/17	64 2/17	-29 15/17	32 2/17	-15/17	-3 15/17	16 2/17	14 2/17	15 2/17	-15 15/17	46 2/17	-47 15/17	85 2/17	111 2/17	142 2/17	138
-123 15/17	-92 15/17	-66 15/17	62 2/17	-27 15/17	30 2/17	19 2/17	9 2/17	4 2/17	11 2/17	-2 15/17	-13 15/17	44 2/17	-45 15/17	83 2/17	109 2/17	140 2/17	138
136 2/17	-91 15/17	-65 15/17	-41 15/17	40 2/17	-9 15/17	18 2/17	10 2/17	8 2/17	6 2/17	-1 15/17	26 2/17	-23 15/17	58 2/17	82 2/17	108 2/17	-119 15/17	138
134 2/17	103 2/17	77 2/17	-39 15/17	38 2/17	-7 15/17	3 2/17	5 2/17	12 2/17	7 2/17	13 2/17	24 2/17	-21 15/17	56 2/17	-60 15/17	-86 15/17	-117 15/17	138
132 2/17	101 2/17	75 2/17	-37 15/17	36 2/17	-5 15/17	1 2/17	20 2/17	2/17	2 2/17	17 2/17	22 2/17	-19 15/17	54 2/17	-58 15/17	-84 15/17	-115 15/17	138
130 2/17	99 2/17	73 2/17	-35 15/17	34 2/17	27 2/17	21 2/17	23 2/17	-11 15/17	-12 15/17	-14 15/17	25 2/17	-17 15/17	52 2/17	-56 15/17	-82 15/17	-113 15/17	138
128 2/17	97 2/17	71 2/17	-33 15/17	32 2/17	-30 15/17	-28 15/17	-26 15/17	-25 15/17	37 2/17	35 2/17	33 2/17	41 2/17	50 2/17	-54 15/17	-80 15/17	-111 15/17	138
126 2/17	95 2/17	69 2/17	59 2/17	49 2/17	51 2/17	53 2/17	55 2/17	-43 15/17	-44 15/17	-46 15/17	-48 15/17	-50 15/17	57 2/17	-52 15/17	-78 15/17	-109 15/17	138
124 2/17	93 2/17	81 2/17	-53 15/17	-55 15/17	-57 15/17	-59 15/17	-61 15/17	-63 15/17	84 2/17	86 2/17	88 2/17	90 2/17	92 2/17	-62 15/17	-76 15/17	-107 15/17	138
122 2/17	107 2/17	-77 15/17	-79 15/17	-81 15/17	-83 15/17	-85 15/17	-87 15/17	-89 15/17	110 2/17	112 2/17	114 2/17	116 2/17	118 2/17	120 2/17	-88 15/17	-105 15/17	138
135 2/17	-134 15/17	-132 15/17	-130 15/17	-128 15/17	-126 15/17	-124 15/17	-122 15/17	-121 15/17	133 2/17	131 2/17	129 2/17	127 2/17	125 2/17	123 2/17	121 2/17	137 2/17	138
138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138	138

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{17} = \frac{3 \times 138}{17} = \frac{414}{17}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{17} = \frac{5 \times 138}{17} = \frac{690}{17}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{17} = \frac{7 \times 138}{17} = \frac{966}{17}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{17} = \frac{9 \times 138}{17} = \frac{1242}{17}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{17} = \frac{11 \times 138}{17} = \frac{1518}{17}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13n}{17} = \frac{13 \times 138}{17} = \frac{1794}{17}$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{15n}{17} = \frac{15 \times 138}{17} = \frac{2070}{17}$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 138.$$

Example 12. Let's consider $n = 141$ in (5), we get

-120 12/17	151 5/17	149 5/17	147 5/17	145 5/17	143 5/17	141 5/17	139 5/17	138 5/17	-116 12/17	-114 12/17	-112 12/17	-110 12/17	-108 12/17	-106 12/17	-104 12/17	-118 12/17	141
-135 12/17	105 5/17	94 5/17	96 5/17	98 5/17	100 5/17	102 5/17	104 5/17	106 5/17	-93 12/17	-95 12/17	-97 12/17	-99 12/17	-101 12/17	-103 12/17	-90 12/17	152 5/17	141
-133 12/17	-102 12/17	79 5/17	70 5/17	72 5/17	74 5/17	76 5/17	78 5/17	80 5/17	-67 12/17	-69 12/17	-71 12/17	-73 12/17	-75 12/17	-64 12/17	119 5/17	150 5/17	141
-131 12/17	-100 12/17	-74 12/17	-40 12/17	-32 12/17	-34 12/17	-36 12/17	-38 12/17	60 5/17	61 5/17	63 5/17	65 5/17	67 5/17	-42 12/17	91 5/17	117 5/17	148 5/17	141
-129 12/17	-98 12/17	-72 12/17	68 5/17	-24 12/17	47 5/17	45 5/17	43 5/17	42 5/17	-20 12/17	-18 12/17	-16 12/17	-22 12/17	-51 12/17	89 5/17	115 5/17	146 5/17	141
-127 12/17	-96 12/17	-70 12/17	66 5/17	-31 12/17	-8 12/17	-4 12/17	-6 12/17	28 5/17	29 5/17	31 5/17	-10 12/17	48 5/17	-49 12/17	87 5/17	113 5/17	144 5/17	141
-125 12/17	-94 12/17	-68 12/17	64 5/17	-29 12/17	32 5/17	-12 12/17	-3 12/17	16 5/17	14 5/17	15 5/17	-15 12/17	46 5/17	-47 12/17	85 5/17	111 5/17	142 5/17	141
-123 12/17	-92 12/17	-66 12/17	62 5/17	-27 12/17	30 5/17	19 5/17	9 5/17	4 5/17	11 5/17	-2 12/17	-13 12/17	44 5/17	-45 12/17	83 5/17	109 5/17	140 5/17	141
136 5/17	-91 12/17	-65 12/17	-41 12/17	40 5/17	-9 12/17	18 5/17	10 5/17	8 5/17	6 5/17	-1 12/17	26 5/17	-23 12/17	58 5/17	82 5/17	108 5/17	-119 12/17	141
134 5/17	103 5/17	77 5/17	-39 12/17	38 5/17	-7 12/17	3 5/17	5 5/17	12 5/17	7 5/17	13 5/17	24 5/17	-21 12/17	56 5/17	-60 12/17	-86 12/17	-117 12/17	141
132 5/17	101 5/17	75 5/17	-37 12/17	36 5/17	-5 12/17	1 5/17	20 5/17	5/17	2 5/17	17 5/17	22 5/17	-19 12/17	54 5/17	-58 12/17	-84 12/17	-115 12/17	141
130 5/17	99 5/17	73 5/17	-35 12/17	34 5/17	27 5/17	21 5/17	23 5/17	-11 12/17	-12 12/17	-14 12/17	25 5/17	-17 12/17	52 5/17	-56 12/17	-82 12/17	-113 12/17	141
128 5/17	97 5/17	71 5/17	-33 12/17	39 5/17	-30 12/17	-28 12/17	-26 12/17	-25 12/17	37 5/17	35 5/17	33 5/17	41 5/17	50 5/17	-54 12/17	-80 12/17	-111 12/17	141
126 5/17	95 5/17	69 5/17	59 5/17	49 5/17	51 5/17	53 5/17	55 5/17	-43 12/17	-44 12/17	-46 12/17	-48 12/17	-50 12/17	57 5/17	-52 12/17	-78 12/17	-109 12/17	141
124 5/17	93 5/17	81 5/17	-53 12/17	-55 12/17	-57 12/17	-59 12/17	-61 12/17	-63 12/17	84 5/17	86 5/17	88 5/17	90 5/17	92 5/17	-62 12/17	-76 12/17	-107 12/17	141
122 5/17	107 5/17	-77 12/17	-79 12/17	-81 12/17	-83 12/17	-85 12/17	-87 12/17	-89 12/17	110 5/17	112 5/17	114 5/17	116 5/17	118 5/17	120 5/17	-88 12/17	-105 12/17	141
135 5/17	-134 12/17	-132 12/17	-130 12/17	-128 12/17	-126 12/17	-124 12/17	-122 12/17	-121 12/17	133 5/17	131 5/17	129 5/17	127 5/17	125 5/17	123 5/17	121 5/17	137 5/17	141
141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{17} = \frac{3 \times 141}{17} = \frac{423}{17}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{17} = \frac{5 \times 141}{17} = \frac{705}{17}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{17} = \frac{7 \times 141}{17} = \frac{987}{17}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{17} = \frac{9 \times 141}{17} = \frac{1269}{17}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{17} = \frac{11 \times 141}{17} = \frac{1551}{17}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13n}{17} = \frac{13 \times 141}{17} = \frac{1833}{17}$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{15n}{17} = \frac{15 \times 141}{17} = \frac{2115}{17}$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 141.$$

Example 13. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 17 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 288, 289\}$, the magic sum is 2465. Considering $n = 2465$ in (5), we get **positive entries nested magic square** of order 17 given by

																	2465
16	288	286	284	282	280	278	276	275	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	18	2465
1	242	231	233	235	237	239	241	243	43	41	39	37	35	33	46	289	2465
3	34	216	207	209	211	213	215	217	69	67	65	63	61	72	256	287	2465
5	36	62	96	104	102	100	98	197	198	200	202	204	94	228	254	285	2465
7	38	64	205	112	184	182	180	179	116	118	120	114	85	226	252	283	2465
9	40	66	203	105	128	132	130	165	166	168	126	185	87	224	250	281	2465
11	42	68	201	107	169	136	133	153	151	152	121	183	89	222	248	279	2465
13	44	70	199	109	167	156	146	141	148	134	123	181	91	220	246	277	2465
273	45	71	95	177	127	155	147	145	143	135	163	113	195	219	245	17	2465
271	240	214	97	175	129	140	142	149	144	150	161	115	193	76	50	19	2465
269	238	212	99	173	131	138	157	137	139	154	159	117	191	78	52	21	2465
267	236	210	101	171	164	158	160	125	124	122	162	119	189	80	54	23	2465
265	234	208	103	176	106	108	110	111	174	172	170	178	187	82	56	25	2465
263	232	206	196	186	188	190	192	93	92	90	88	86	194	84	58	27	2465
261	230	218	83	81	79	77	75	73	221	223	225	227	229	74	60	29	2465
259	244	59	57	55	53	51	49	47	247	249	251	253	255	257	48	31	2465
272	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	15	270	268	266	264	262	260	258	274	2465
2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465	2465

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{17} = \frac{3 \times 2465}{17} = 435$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{17} = \frac{5 \times 2465}{17} = 725$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{17} = \frac{7 \times 2465}{17} = 1015$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{17} = \frac{9 \times 2465}{17} = 1305$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{17} = \frac{11 \times 2465}{17} = 1595$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13n}{17} = \frac{13 \times 2465}{17} = 1885$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{15n}{17} = \frac{15 \times 2465}{17} = 2175$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 2465.$$

2.5 Nested Magic Square of Order 16

Result 5. *Nested magic square of order 16 with symmetric entries and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by*

$113.5+.0625n$	$-106.5+.0625n$	$107.5+.0625n$	$-108.5+.0625n$	$-109.5+.0625n$	$110.5+.0625n$	$111.5+.0625n$	$120.5+.0625n$	$105.5+.0625n$	$-114.5+.0625n$	$-115.5+.0625n$	$116.5+.0625n$	$-117.5+.0625n$	$118.5+.0625n$	$-119.5+.0625n$	$-112.5+.0625n$	n
$126.5+.0625n$	$-84.5+.0625n$	$-90.5+.0625n$	$89.5+.0625n$	$-88.5+.0625n$	$87.5+.0625n$	$-86.5+.0625n$	$97.5+.0625n$	$-91.5+.0625n$	$83.5+.0625n$	$-82.5+.0625n$	$81.5+.0625n$	$-80.5+.0625n$	$79.5+.0625n$	$85.5+.0625n$	$-126.5+.0625n$	n
$-125.5+.0625n$	$96.5+.0625n$	$61.5+.0625n$	$70.5+.0625n$	$-69.5+.0625n$	$68.5+.0625n$	$-67.5+.0625n$	$-71.5+.0625n$	$-50.5+.0625n$	$51.5+.0625n$	$-52.5+.0625n$	$53.5+.0625n$	$-54.5+.0625n$	$60.5+.0625n$	$-96.5+.0625n$	$125.5+.0625n$	n
$124.5+.0625n$	$-95.5+.0625n$	$-56.5+.0625n$	$40.5+.0625n$	$35.5+.0625n$	$-34.5+.0625n$	$33.5+.0625n$	$-32.5+.0625n$	$-36.5+.0625n$	$-46.5+.0625n$	$47.5+.0625n$	$-48.5+.0625n$	$41.5+.0625n$	$56.5+.0625n$	$95.5+.0625n$	$-124.5+.0625n$	n
$-123.5+.0625n$	$94.5+.0625n$	$-57.5+.0625n$	$-37.5+.0625n$	$-24.5+.0625n$	$-30.5+.0625n$	$29.5+.0625n$	$31.5+.0625n$	$18.5+.0625n$	$-19.5+.0625n$	$20.5+.0625n$	$-25.5+.0625n$	$37.5+.0625n$	$57.5+.0625n$	$-94.5+.0625n$	$123.5+.0625n$	n
$122.5+.0625n$	$-93.5+.0625n$	$58.5+.0625n$	$38.5+.0625n$	$-27.5+.0625n$	$13.5+.0625n$	$11.5+.0625n$	$-15.5+.0625n$	$17.5+.0625n$	$-14.5+.0625n$	$-12.5+.0625n$	$27.5+.0625n$	$-38.5+.0625n$	$-58.5+.0625n$	$93.5+.0625n$	$-122.5+.0625n$	n
$-121.5+.0625n$	$92.5+.0625n$	$59.5+.0625n$	$-39.5+.0625n$	$-26.5+.0625n$	$-16.5+.0625n$	$5.5+.0625n$	$-7.5+.0625n$	$-4.5+.0625n$	$6.5+.0625n$	$16.5+.0625n$	$26.5+.0625n$	$39.5+.0625n$	$-59.5+.0625n$	$-92.5+.0625n$	$121.5+.0625n$	n
$-127.5+.0625n$	$78.5+.0625n$	$66.5+.0625n$	$45.5+.0625n$	$-21.5+.0625n$	$-10.5+.0625n$	$-1.5+.0625n$	$3.5+.0625n$	$0.5+.0625n$	$-2.5+.0625n$	$10.5+.0625n$	$21.5+.0625n$	$-45.5+.0625n$	$-66.5+.0625n$	$-78.5+.0625n$	$127.5+.0625n$	n
$-98.5+.0625n$	$72.5+.0625n$	$55.5+.0625n$	$-49.5+.0625n$	$28.5+.0625n$	$-8.5+.0625n$	$2.5+.0625n$	$-0.5+.0625n$	$-3.5+.0625n$	$1.5+.0625n$	$8.5+.0625n$	$-28.5+.0625n$	$49.5+.0625n$	$-55.5+.0625n$	$-72.5+.0625n$	$98.5+.0625n$	n
$99.5+.0625n$	$-73.5+.0625n$	$-62.5+.0625n$	$42.5+.0625n$	$23.5+.0625n$	$9.5+.0625n$	$-6.5+.0625n$	$4.5+.0625n$	$7.5+.0625n$	$-5.5+.0625n$	$-9.5+.0625n$	$-23.5+.0625n$	$-42.5+.0625n$	$62.5+.0625n$	$73.5+.0625n$	$-99.5+.0625n$	n
$-100.5+.0625n$	$74.5+.0625n$	$-63.5+.0625n$	$-43.5+.0625n$	$22.5+.0625n$	$12.5+.0625n$	$-11.5+.0625n$	$15.5+.0625n$	$-17.5+.0625n$	$14.5+.0625n$	$-13.5+.0625n$	$-22.5+.0625n$	$43.5+.0625n$	$63.5+.0625n$	$-74.5+.0625n$	$100.5+.0625n$	n
$101.5+.0625n$	$-75.5+.0625n$	$64.5+.0625n$	$44.5+.0625n$	$25.5+.0625n$	$30.5+.0625n$	$-29.5+.0625n$	$-31.5+.0625n$	$-18.5+.0625n$	$19.5+.0625n$	$-20.5+.0625n$	$24.5+.0625n$	$-44.5+.0625n$	$-64.5+.0625n$	$75.5+.0625n$	$-101.5+.0625n$	n
$-102.5+.0625n$	$76.5+.0625n$	$-65.5+.0625n$	$-41.5+.0625n$	$-35.5+.0625n$	$34.5+.0625n$	$-33.5+.0625n$	$32.5+.0625n$	$36.5+.0625n$	$46.5+.0625n$	$-47.5+.0625n$	$48.5+.0625n$	$-40.5+.0625n$	$65.5+.0625n$	$-76.5+.0625n$	$102.5+.0625n$	n
$103.5+.0625n$	$-77.5+.0625n$	$-60.5+.0625n$	$-70.5+.0625n$	$69.5+.0625n$	$-68.5+.0625n$	$67.5+.0625n$	$71.5+.0625n$	$50.5+.0625n$	$-51.5+.0625n$	$52.5+.0625n$	$-53.5+.0625n$	$54.5+.0625n$	$-61.5+.0625n$	$77.5+.0625n$	$-103.5+.0625n$	n
$-104.5+.0625n$	$-85.5+.0625n$	$90.5+.0625n$	$-89.5+.0625n$	$88.5+.0625n$	$-87.5+.0625n$	$86.5+.0625n$	$-97.5+.0625n$	$91.5+.0625n$	$-83.5+.0625n$	$82.5+.0625n$	$-81.5+.0625n$	$80.5+.0625n$	$-79.5+.0625n$	$84.5+.0625n$	$104.5+.0625n$	n
$112.5+.0625n$	$106.5+.0625n$	$-107.5+.0625n$	$108.5+.0625n$	$109.5+.0625n$	$-110.5+.0625n$	$-111.5+.0625n$	$-120.5+.0625n$	$-105.5+.0625n$	$114.5+.0625n$	$115.5+.0625n$	$-116.5+.0625n$	$117.5+.0625n$	$-118.5+.0625n$	$119.5+.0625n$	$-113.5+.0625n$	n
n	n															

(6)

In this case, the magic sums are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4n}{16} = \frac{n}{4} & S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10n}{16} = \frac{5n}{8} \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6n}{16} = \frac{3n}{8} & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12n}{16} = \frac{3n}{4} \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8n}{16} = \frac{n}{2} & S_{14 \times 14} &:= \frac{14n}{16} = \frac{7n}{8} \\
 & & S_{16 \times 16} &:= \frac{16n}{16} = n.
 \end{aligned}$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{\pm 0.5, \pm 1.5, \dots, \pm 126.5 \pm 127.5\}$.

Example 14. Let's consider $n = 131$ in (6), we get

121.6875	-98.3125	115.6875	-100.3125	-101.3125	118.6875	119.6875	128.6875	113.6875	-106.3125	-107.3125	124.6875	-109.3125	126.6875	-111.3125	-104.3125	131
134.6875	-76.3125	-82.3125	97.6875	-80.3125	95.6875	-78.3125	105.6875	-83.3125	91.6875	-74.3125	89.6875	-72.3125	87.6875	93.6875	-118.3125	131
-117.3125	104.6875	69.6875	78.6875	-61.3125	76.6875	-59.3125	-63.3125	-42.3125	59.6875	-44.3125	61.6875	-46.3125	68.6875	-88.3125	133.6875	131
132.6875	-87.3125	-48.3125	48.6875	43.6875	-26.3125	41.6875	-24.3125	-28.3125	-38.3125	55.6875	-40.3125	49.6875	64.6875	103.6875	-116.3125	131
-115.3125	102.6875	-49.3125	-29.3125	-16.3125	-22.3125	37.6875	39.6875	26.6875	-11.3125	28.6875	-17.3125	45.6875	65.6875	-86.3125	131.6875	131
130.6875	-85.3125	66.6875	46.6875	-19.3125	21.6875	19.6875	-7.3125	25.6875	-6.3125	-4.3125	35.6875	-30.3125	-50.3125	101.6875	-114.3125	131
-113.3125	100.6875	67.6875	-31.3125	-18.3125	-8.3125	13.6875	0.6875	3.6875	14.6875	24.6875	34.6875	47.6875	-51.3125	-84.3125	129.6875	131
-119.3125	86.6875	74.6875	53.6875	-13.3125	-2.3125	6.6875	11.6875	8.6875	5.6875	18.6875	29.6875	-37.3125	-58.3125	-70.3125	135.6875	131
-90.3125	80.6875	63.6875	-41.3125	36.6875	-0.3125	10.6875	7.6875	4.6875	9.6875	16.6875	-20.3125	57.6875	-47.3125	-64.3125	106.6875	131
107.6875	-65.3125	-54.3125	50.6875	31.6875	17.6875	1.6875	12.6875	15.6875	2.6875	-1.3125	-15.3125	-34.3125	70.6875	81.6875	-91.3125	131
-92.3125	82.6875	-55.3125	-35.3125	30.6875	20.6875	-3.3125	23.6875	-9.3125	22.6875	-5.3125	-14.3125	51.6875	71.6875	-66.3125	108.6875	131
109.6875	-67.3125	72.6875	52.6875	33.6875	38.6875	-21.3125	-23.3125	-10.3125	27.6875	-12.3125	32.6875	-36.3125	-56.3125	83.6875	-93.3125	131
-94.3125	84.6875	-57.3125	-33.3125	-27.3125	42.6875	-25.3125	40.6875	44.6875	54.6875	-39.3125	56.6875	-32.3125	73.6875	-68.3125	110.6875	131
111.6875	-69.3125	-52.3125	-62.3125	77.6875	-60.3125	75.6875	79.6875	58.6875	-43.3125	60.6875	-45.3125	62.6875	-53.3125	85.6875	-95.3125	131
-96.3125	-77.3125	98.6875	-81.3125	96.6875	-79.3125	94.6875	-89.3125	99.6875	-75.3125	90.6875	-73.3125	88.6875	-71.3125	92.6875	112.6875	131
120.6875	114.6875	-99.3125	116.6875	117.6875	-102.3125	-103.3125	-112.3125	-97.3125	122.6875	123.6875	-108.3125	125.6875	-110.3125	127.6875	-105.3125	131
131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{16} = \frac{4 \times 131}{16} = 32.75$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{16} = \frac{6 \times 131}{16} = 49.125$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{16} = \frac{8 \times 131}{16} = 65.5$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10n}{16} = \frac{10 \times 131}{16} = 81.875$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := \frac{12n}{16} = \frac{12 \times 131}{16} = 98.25$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := \frac{14n}{16} = \frac{14 \times 131}{16} = 114.625$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 131.$$

Example 15. Let's consider $n = 137$ in (6), we get

122.0625	-97.9375	116.0625	-99.9375	-100.9375	119.0625	120.0625	129.0625	114.0625	-105.9375	-106.9375	125.0625	-108.9375	127.0625	-110.9375	-103.9375	137
135.0625	-75.9375	-81.9375	98.0625	-79.9375	96.0625	-77.9375	106.0625	-82.9375	92.0625	-73.9375	90.0625	-71.9375	88.0625	94.0625	-117.9375	137
-116.9375	105.0625	70.0625	79.0625	-60.9375	77.0625	-58.9375	-62.9375	-41.9375	60.0625	-43.9375	62.0625	-45.9375	69.0625	-87.9375	134.0625	137
133.0625	-86.9375	-47.9375	49.0625	44.0625	-25.9375	42.0625	-23.9375	-27.9375	-37.9375	56.0625	-39.9375	50.0625	65.0625	104.0625	-115.9375	137
-114.9375	103.0625	-48.9375	-28.9375	-15.9375	-21.9375	38.0625	40.0625	27.0625	-10.9375	29.0625	-16.9375	46.0625	66.0625	-85.9375	132.0625	137
131.0625	-84.9375	67.0625	47.0625	-18.9375	22.0625	20.0625	-6.9375	26.0625	-5.9375	-3.9375	36.0625	-29.9375	-49.9375	102.0625	-113.9375	137
-112.9375	101.0625	68.0625	-30.9375	-17.9375	-7.9375	14.0625	1.0625	4.0625	15.0625	25.0625	35.0625	48.0625	-50.9375	-83.9375	130.0625	137
-118.9375	87.0625	75.0625	54.0625	-12.9375	-1.9375	7.0625	12.0625	9.0625	6.0625	19.0625	30.0625	-36.9375	-57.9375	-69.9375	136.0625	137
-89.9375	81.0625	64.0625	-40.9375	37.0625	0.0625	11.0625	8.0625	5.0625	10.0625	17.0625	-19.9375	58.0625	-46.9375	-63.9375	107.0625	137
108.0625	-64.9375	-53.9375	51.0625	32.0625	18.0625	2.0625	13.0625	16.0625	3.0625	-0.9375	-14.9375	-33.9375	71.0625	82.0625	-90.9375	137
-91.9375	83.0625	-54.9375	-34.9375	31.0625	21.0625	-2.9375	24.0625	-8.9375	23.0625	-4.9375	-13.9375	52.0625	72.0625	-65.9375	109.0625	137
110.0625	-66.9375	73.0625	53.0625	34.0625	39.0625	-20.9375	-22.9375	-9.9375	28.0625	-11.9375	33.0625	-35.9375	-55.9375	84.0625	-92.9375	137
-93.9375	85.0625	-56.9375	-32.9375	-26.9375	43.0625	-24.9375	41.0625	45.0625	55.0625	-38.9375	57.0625	-31.9375	74.0625	-67.9375	111.0625	137
112.0625	-68.9375	-51.9375	-61.9375	78.0625	-59.9375	76.0625	80.0625	59.0625	-42.9375	61.0625	-44.9375	63.0625	-52.9375	86.0625	-94.9375	137
-95.9375	-76.9375	99.0625	-80.9375	97.0625	-78.9375	95.0625	-88.9375	100.0625	-74.9375	91.0625	-72.9375	89.0625	-70.9375	93.0625	113.0625	137
121.0625	115.0625	-98.9375	117.0625	118.0625	-101.9375	-102.9375	-111.9375	-96.9375	123.0625	124.0625	-107.9375	126.0625	-109.9375	128.0625	-104.9375	137
137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{16} = \frac{4 \times 137}{16} = 34.25$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{16} = \frac{6 \times 137}{16} = 51.375$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{16} = \frac{8 \times 137}{16} = 68.5$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10n}{16} = \frac{10 \times 137}{16} = 85.625$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := \frac{12n}{16} = \frac{12 \times 137}{16} = 102.75$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := \frac{14n}{16} = \frac{14 \times 137}{16} = 119.875$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 137.$$

Example 16. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 16 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 255, 256\}$, the magic sum is 2056. Considering $n = 2056$ in (6), we get **positive entries nested magic square** of order 16 given by

242	22	236	20	19	239	240	249	234	14	13	245	11	247	9	16	2056
255	44	38	218	40	216	42	226	37	212	46	210	48	208	214	2	2056
3	225	190	199	59	197	61	57	78	180	76	182	74	189	32	254	2056
253	33	72	169	164	94	162	96	92	82	176	80	170	185	224	4	2056
5	223	71	91	104	98	158	160	147	109	149	103	166	186	34	252	2056
251	35	187	167	101	142	140	113	146	114	116	156	90	70	222	6	2056
7	221	188	89	102	112	134	121	124	135	145	155	168	69	36	250	2056
1	207	195	174	107	118	127	132	129	126	139	150	83	62	50	256	2056
30	201	184	79	157	120	131	128	125	130	137	100	178	73	56	227	2056
228	55	66	171	152	138	122	133	136	123	119	105	86	191	202	29	2056
28	203	65	85	151	141	117	144	111	143	115	106	172	192	54	229	2056
230	53	193	173	154	159	99	97	110	148	108	153	84	64	204	27	2056
26	205	63	87	93	163	95	161	165	175	81	177	88	194	52	231	2056
232	51	68	58	198	60	196	200	179	77	181	75	183	67	206	25	2056
24	43	219	39	217	41	215	31	220	45	211	47	209	49	213	233	2056
241	235	21	237	238	18	17	8	23	243	244	12	246	10	248	15	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{16} = \frac{4 \times 2056}{16} = 514$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{16} = \frac{6 \times 2056}{16} = 771$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{16} = \frac{8 \times 2056}{16} = 1028$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10n}{16} = \frac{10 \times 2056}{16} = 1285$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := \frac{12n}{16} = \frac{12 \times 2056}{16} = 1542$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := \frac{14n}{16} = \frac{14 \times 2056}{16} = 1799$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 2056.$$

2.6 Nested Magic Square of Order 15

Result 6. Nested magic square of order 15 with *symmetric entries* and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by

$97+n/15$	$86+n/15$	$88+n/15$	$90+n/15$	$92+n/15$	$94+n/15$	$96+n/15$	$98+n/15$	$-102+n/15$	$-104+n/15$	$-106+n/15$	$-108+n/15$	$-110+n/15$	$-112+n/15$	$-99+n/15$	n
$-111+n/15$	$71+n/15$	$62+n/15$	$64+n/15$	$66+n/15$	$68+n/15$	$70+n/15$	$72+n/15$	$-76+n/15$	$-78+n/15$	$-80+n/15$	$-82+n/15$	$-84+n/15$	$-73+n/15$	$111+n/15$	n
$-109+n/15$	$-83+n/15$	$-49+n/15$	$-41+n/15$	$-43+n/15$	$-45+n/15$	$-47+n/15$	$52+n/15$	$53+n/15$	$55+n/15$	$57+n/15$	$59+n/15$	$-51+n/15$	$83+n/15$	$109+n/15$	n
$-107+n/15$	$-81+n/15$	$60+n/15$	$-33+n/15$	$39+n/15$	$37+n/15$	$35+n/15$	$34+n/15$	$-29+n/15$	$-27+n/15$	$-25+n/15$	$-31+n/15$	$-60+n/15$	$81+n/15$	$107+n/15$	n
$-105+n/15$	$-79+n/15$	$58+n/15$	$-40+n/15$	$-17+n/15$	$-13+n/15$	$-15+n/15$	$20+n/15$	$21+n/15$	$23+n/15$	$-19+n/15$	$40+n/15$	$-58+n/15$	$79+n/15$	$105+n/15$	n
$-103+n/15$	$-77+n/15$	$56+n/15$	$-38+n/15$	$24+n/15$	$-9+n/15$	$-12+n/15$	$8+n/15$	$6+n/15$	$7+n/15$	$-24+n/15$	$38+n/15$	$-56+n/15$	$77+n/15$	$103+n/15$	n
$-101+n/15$	$-75+n/15$	$54+n/15$	$-36+n/15$	$22+n/15$	$11+n/15$	$1+n/15$	$-4+n/15$	$3+n/15$	$-11+n/15$	$-22+n/15$	$36+n/15$	$-54+n/15$	$75+n/15$	$101+n/15$	n
$-100+n/15$	$-74+n/15$	$-50+n/15$	$32+n/15$	$-18+n/15$	$10+n/15$	$2+n/15$	$0+n/15$	$-2+n/15$	$-10+n/15$	$18+n/15$	$-32+n/15$	$50+n/15$	$74+n/15$	$100+n/15$	n
$95+n/15$	$69+n/15$	$-48+n/15$	$30+n/15$	$-16+n/15$	$-5+n/15$	$-3+n/15$	$4+n/15$	$-1+n/15$	$5+n/15$	$16+n/15$	$-30+n/15$	$48+n/15$	$-69+n/15$	$-95+n/15$	n
$93+n/15$	$67+n/15$	$-46+n/15$	$28+n/15$	$-14+n/15$	$-7+n/15$	$12+n/15$	$-8+n/15$	$-6+n/15$	$9+n/15$	$14+n/15$	$-28+n/15$	$46+n/15$	$-67+n/15$	$-93+n/15$	n
$91+n/15$	$65+n/15$	$-44+n/15$	$26+n/15$	$19+n/15$	$13+n/15$	$15+n/15$	$-20+n/15$	$-21+n/15$	$-23+n/15$	$17+n/15$	$-26+n/15$	$44+n/15$	$-65+n/15$	$-91+n/15$	n
$89+n/15$	$63+n/15$	$-42+n/15$	$31+n/15$	$-39+n/15$	$-37+n/15$	$-35+n/15$	$-34+n/15$	$29+n/15$	$27+n/15$	$25+n/15$	$33+n/15$	$42+n/15$	$-63+n/15$	$-89+n/15$	n
$87+n/15$	$61+n/15$	$51+n/15$	$41+n/15$	$43+n/15$	$45+n/15$	$47+n/15$	$-52+n/15$	$-53+n/15$	$-55+n/15$	$-57+n/15$	$-59+n/15$	$49+n/15$	$-61+n/15$	$-87+n/15$	n
$85+n/15$	$73+n/15$	$-62+n/15$	$-64+n/15$	$-66+n/15$	$-68+n/15$	$-70+n/15$	$-72+n/15$	$76+n/15$	$78+n/15$	$80+n/15$	$82+n/15$	$84+n/15$	$-71+n/15$	$-85+n/15$	n
$99+n/15$	$-86+n/15$	$-88+n/15$	$-90+n/15$	$-92+n/15$	$-94+n/15$	$-96+n/15$	$-98+n/15$	$102+n/15$	$104+n/15$	$106+n/15$	$108+n/15$	$110+n/15$	$112+n/15$	$-97+n/15$	n
n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n	n

(7)

In this case, the magic sums are given by,

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{15}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{15}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{15}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{15}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{15}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13n}{15}$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := n$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm 111, \pm 112\}$.

Example 17. Let's consider $n = 132$ in (7), we get

105.8	94.8	96.8	98.8	101	103	105	107	-93.2	-95.2	-97.2	-99.2	-101	-103	-90.2	132
-102	79.8	70.8	72.8	74.8	76.8	78.8	80.8	-67.2	-69.2	-71.2	-73.2	-75.2	-64.2	120	132
-100	-74	-40	-32	-34.2	-36.2	-38.2	60.8	61.8	63.8	65.8	67.8	-42.2	91.8	118	132
-98.2	-72	68.8	-24	47.8	45.8	43.8	42.8	-20.2	-18.2	-16.2	-22.2	-51.2	89.8	116	132
-96.2	-70	66.8	-31	-8.2	-4.2	-6.2	28.8	29.8	31.8	-10.2	48.8	-49.2	87.8	114	132
-94.2	-68	64.8	-29	32.8	-0.2	-3.2	16.8	14.8	15.8	-15.2	46.8	-47.2	85.8	112	132
-92.2	-66	62.8	-27	30.8	19.8	9.8	4.8	11.8	-2.2	-13.2	44.8	-45.2	83.8	110	132
-91.2	-65	-41	40.8	-9.2	18.8	10.8	8.8	6.8	-1.2	26.8	-23.2	58.8	82.8	109	132
103.8	77.8	-39	38.8	-7.2	3.8	5.8	12.8	7.8	13.8	24.8	-21.2	56.8	-60.2	-86.2	132
101.8	75.8	-37	36.8	-5.2	1.8	20.8	0.8	2.8	17.8	22.8	-19.2	54.8	-58.2	-84.2	132
99.8	73.8	-35	34.8	27.8	21.8	23.8	-11.2	-12.2	-14.2	25.8	-17.2	52.8	-56.2	-82.2	132
97.8	71.8	-33	39.8	-30.2	-28.2	-26.2	-25.2	37.8	35.8	33.8	41.8	50.8	-54.2	-80.2	132
95.8	69.8	59.8	49.8	51.8	53.8	55.8	-43.2	-44.2	-46.2	-48.2	-50.2	57.8	-52.2	-78.2	132
93.8	81.8	-53	-55	-57.2	-59.2	-61.2	-63.2	84.8	86.8	88.8	90.8	92.8	-62.2	-76.2	132
107.8	-77	-79	-81	-83.2	-85.2	-87.2	-89.2	111	113	115	117	118.8	120.8	-88.2	132
132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{15} = \frac{3 \times 132}{15} = 26.4$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{15} = \frac{5 \times 132}{15} = 44$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{15} = \frac{7 \times 132}{15} = 61.6$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{15} = \frac{9 \times 132}{15} = 79.2$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{15} = \frac{11 \times 132}{15} = 96.8$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13n}{15} = \frac{13 \times 132}{15} = 114.4$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 132.$$

Example 18. Let's consider $n = 135$ in (7), we get

106	95	97	99	101	103	105	107	-93	-95	-97	-99	-101	-103	-90	135
-102	80	71	73	75	77	79	81	-67	-69	-71	-73	-75	-64	120	135
-100	-74	-40	-32	-34	-36	-38	61	62	64	66	68	-42	92	118	135
-98	-72	69	-24	48	46	44	43	-20	-18	-16	-22	-51	90	116	135
-96	-70	67	-31	-8	-4	-6	29	30	32	-10	49	-49	88	114	135
-94	-68	65	-29	33	0	-3	17	15	16	-15	47	-47	86	112	135
-92	-66	63	-27	31	20	10	5	12	-2	-13	45	-45	84	110	135
-91	-65	-41	41	-9	19	11	9	7	-1	27	-23	59	83	109	135
104	78	-39	39	-7	4	6	13	8	14	25	-21	57	-60	-86	135
102	76	-37	37	-5	2	21	1	3	18	23	-19	55	-58	-84	135
100	74	-35	35	28	22	24	-11	-12	-14	26	-17	53	-56	-82	135
98	72	-33	40	-30	-28	-26	-25	38	36	34	42	51	-54	-80	135
96	70	60	50	52	54	56	-43	-44	-46	-48	-50	58	-52	-78	135
94	82	-53	-55	-57	-59	-61	-63	85	87	89	91	93	-62	-76	135
108	-77	-79	-81	-83	-85	-87	-89	111	113	115	117	119	121	-88	135
135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{15} = \frac{3 \times 135}{15} = 27$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{15} = \frac{5 \times 135}{15} = 45$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{15} = \frac{7 \times 135}{15} = 63$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{15} = \frac{9 \times 135}{15} = 81$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{15} = \frac{11 \times 135}{15} = 99$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13n}{15} = \frac{13 \times 135}{15} = 117$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 135.$$

Example 19. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 15 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 224, 225\}$, the magic sum is 1695. Considering $n = 1695$ in (7), we get **positive entries nested magic square** of order 15 given by

															1695
210	199	201	203	205	207	209	211	11	9	7	5	3	1	14	1695
2	184	175	177	179	181	183	185	37	35	33	31	29	40	224	1695
4	30	64	72	70	68	66	165	166	168	170	172	62	196	222	1695
6	32	173	80	152	150	148	147	84	86	88	82	53	194	220	1695
8	34	171	73	96	100	98	133	134	136	94	153	55	192	218	1695
10	36	169	75	137	104	101	121	119	120	89	151	57	190	216	1695
12	38	167	77	135	124	114	109	116	102	91	149	59	188	214	1695
13	39	63	145	95	123	115	113	111	103	131	81	163	187	213	1695
208	182	65	143	97	108	110	117	112	118	129	83	161	44	18	1695
206	180	67	141	99	106	125	105	107	122	127	85	159	46	20	1695
204	178	69	139	132	126	128	93	92	90	130	87	157	48	22	1695
202	176	71	144	74	76	78	79	142	140	138	146	155	50	24	1695
200	174	164	154	156	158	160	61	60	58	56	54	162	52	26	1695
198	186	51	49	47	45	43	41	189	191	193	195	197	42	28	1695
212	27	25	23	21	19	17	15	215	217	219	221	223	225	16	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{15} = \frac{3 \times 1695}{15} = 339$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{15} = \frac{5 \times 1695}{15} = 565$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{15} = \frac{7 \times 1695}{15} = 791$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{15} = \frac{9 \times 1695}{15} = 1017$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{15} = \frac{11 \times 1695}{15} = 1243$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := \frac{13n}{15} = \frac{13 \times 1695}{15} = 1469$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 1695.$$

2.7 Nested Magic Square of Order 14

Result 7. Nested magic square of order 14 with *symmetric entries* and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by

$-84.5+n/14$	$-90.5+n/14$	$89.5+n/14$	$-88.5+n/14$	$87.5+n/14$	$-86.5+n/14$	$97.5+n/14$	$-91.5+n/14$	$83.5+n/14$	$-82.5+n/14$	$81.5+n/14$	$-80.5+n/14$	$79.5+n/14$	$85.5+n/14$
$96.5+n/14$	$61.5+n/14$	$70.5+n/14$	$-69.5+n/14$	$68.5+n/14$	$-67.5+n/14$	$-71.5+n/14$	$-50.5+n/14$	$51.5+n/14$	$-52.5+n/14$	$53.5+n/14$	$-54.5+n/14$	$60.5+n/14$	$-96.5+n/14$
$-95.5+n/14$	$-56.5+n/14$	$40.5+n/14$	$35.5+n/14$	$-34.5+n/14$	$33.5+n/14$	$-32.5+n/14$	$-36.5+n/14$	$-46.5+n/14$	$47.5+n/14$	$-48.5+n/14$	$41.5+n/14$	$56.5+n/14$	$95.5+n/14$
$94.5+n/14$	$-57.5+n/14$	$-37.5+n/14$	$-24.5+n/14$	$-30.5+n/14$	$29.5+n/14$	$31.5+n/14$	$18.5+n/14$	$-19.5+n/14$	$20.5+n/14$	$-25.5+n/14$	$37.5+n/14$	$57.5+n/14$	$-94.5+n/14$
$-93.5+n/14$	$58.5+n/14$	$38.5+n/14$	$-27.5+n/14$	$13.5+n/14$	$11.5+n/14$	$-15.5+n/14$	$17.5+n/14$	$-14.5+n/14$	$-12.5+n/14$	$27.5+n/14$	$-38.5+n/14$	$-58.5+n/14$	$93.5+n/14$
$92.5+n/14$	$59.5+n/14$	$-39.5+n/14$	$-26.5+n/14$	$-16.5+n/14$	$5.5+n/14$	$-7.5+n/14$	$-4.5+n/14$	$6.5+n/14$	$16.5+n/14$	$26.5+n/14$	$39.5+n/14$	$-59.5+n/14$	$-92.5+n/14$
$78.5+n/14$	$66.5+n/14$	$45.5+n/14$	$-21.5+n/14$	$-10.5+n/14$	$-1.5+n/14$	$3.5+n/14$	$0.5+n/14$	$-2.5+n/14$	$10.5+n/14$	$21.5+n/14$	$-45.5+n/14$	$-66.5+n/14$	$-78.5+n/14$
$72.5+n/14$	$55.5+n/14$	$-49.5+n/14$	$28.5+n/14$	$-8.5+n/14$	$2.5+n/14$	$-0.5+n/14$	$-3.5+n/14$	$1.5+n/14$	$8.5+n/14$	$-28.5+n/14$	$49.5+n/14$	$-55.5+n/14$	$-72.5+n/14$
$-73.5+n/14$	$-62.5+n/14$	$42.5+n/14$	$23.5+n/14$	$9.5+n/14$	$-6.5+n/14$	$4.5+n/14$	$7.5+n/14$	$-5.5+n/14$	$-9.5+n/14$	$-23.5+n/14$	$-42.5+n/14$	$62.5+n/14$	$73.5+n/14$
$74.5+n/14$	$-63.5+n/14$	$-43.5+n/14$	$22.5+n/14$	$12.5+n/14$	$-11.5+n/14$	$15.5+n/14$	$-17.5+n/14$	$14.5+n/14$	$-13.5+n/14$	$-22.5+n/14$	$43.5+n/14$	$63.5+n/14$	$-74.5+n/14$
$-75.5+n/14$	$64.5+n/14$	$44.5+n/14$	$25.5+n/14$	$30.5+n/14$	$-29.5+n/14$	$-31.5+n/14$	$-18.5+n/14$	$19.5+n/14$	$-20.5+n/14$	$24.5+n/14$	$-44.5+n/14$	$-64.5+n/14$	$75.5+n/14$
$76.5+n/14$	$-65.5+n/14$	$-41.5+n/14$	$-35.5+n/14$	$34.5+n/14$	$-33.5+n/14$	$32.5+n/14$	$36.5+n/14$	$46.5+n/14$	$-47.5+n/14$	$48.5+n/14$	$-40.5+n/14$	$65.5+n/14$	$-76.5+n/14$
$-77.5+n/14$	$-60.5+n/14$	$-70.5+n/14$	$69.5+n/14$	$-68.5+n/14$	$67.5+n/14$	$71.5+n/14$	$50.5+n/14$	$-51.5+n/14$	$52.5+n/14$	$-53.5+n/14$	$54.5+n/14$	$-61.5+n/14$	$77.5+n/14$
$-85.5+n/14$	$90.5+n/14$	$-89.5+n/14$	$88.5+n/14$	$-87.5+n/14$	$86.5+n/14$	$-97.5+n/14$	$91.5+n/14$	$-83.5+n/14$	$82.5+n/14$	$-81.5+n/14$	$80.5+n/14$	$-79.5+n/14$	$84.5+n/14$

(8)

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4n}{14} = \frac{2n}{7} & S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10n}{14} = \frac{5n}{7} \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6n}{14} = \frac{3n}{7} & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12n}{14} = \frac{6n}{7} \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8n}{14} = \frac{4n}{7} & S_{14 \times 14} &:= \frac{146n}{14} = n.
 \end{aligned}$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{\pm 0.5, \pm 1.5, \dots, \pm 96.5 \pm 97.5\}$.

Example 20. Let's consider $n = 133$ in (8), we get

-75	-81	99	-79	97	-77	107	-82	93	-73	91	-71	89	95	133
106	71	80	-60	78	-58	-62	-41	61	-43	63	-45	70	-87	133
-86	-47	50	45	-25	43	-23	-27	-37	57	-39	51	66	105	133
104	-48	-28	-15	-21	39	41	28	-10	30	-16	47	67	-85	133
-84	68	48	-18	23	21	-6	27	-5	-3	37	-29	-49	103	133
102	69	-30	-17	-7	15	2	5	16	26	36	49	-50	-83	133
88	76	55	-12	-1	8	13	10	7	20	31	-36	-57	-69	133
82	65	-40	38	1	12	9	6	11	18	-19	59	-46	-63	133
-64	-53	52	33	19	3	14	17	4	0	-14	-33	72	83	133
84	-54	-34	32	22	-2	25	-8	24	-4	-13	53	73	-65	133
-66	74	54	35	40	-20	-22	-9	29	-11	34	-35	-55	85	133
86	-56	-32	-26	44	-24	42	46	56	-38	58	-31	75	-67	133
-68	-51	-61	79	-59	77	81	60	-42	62	-44	64	-52	87	133
-76	100	-80	98	-78	96	-88	101	-74	92	-72	90	-70	94	133
133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{14} = \frac{4 \times 133}{14} = 38$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{14} = \frac{6 \times 133}{14} = 57$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{14} = \frac{8 \times 133}{14} = 76$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10n}{14} = \frac{10 \times 133}{14} = 95$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := \frac{12n}{14} = \frac{12 \times 133}{14} = 114$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 133.$$

Example 21. Let's consider $n = 140$ in (8), we get

-74.5	-80.5	99.5	-78.5	97.5	-76.5	107.5	-81.5	93.5	-72.5	91.5	-70.5	89.5	95.5	140
106.5	71.5	80.5	-59.5	78.5	-57.5	-61.5	-40.5	61.5	-42.5	63.5	-44.5	70.5	-86.5	140
-85.5	-46.5	50.5	45.5	-24.5	43.5	-22.5	-26.5	-36.5	57.5	-38.5	51.5	66.5	105.5	140
104.5	-47.5	-27.5	-14.5	-20.5	39.5	41.5	28.5	-9.5	30.5	-15.5	47.5	67.5	-84.5	140
-83.5	68.5	48.5	-17.5	23.5	21.5	-5.5	27.5	-4.5	-2.5	37.5	-28.5	-48.5	103.5	140
102.5	69.5	-29.5	-16.5	-6.5	15.5	2.5	5.5	16.5	26.5	36.5	49.5	-49.5	-82.5	140
88.5	76.5	55.5	-11.5	-0.5	8.5	13.5	10.5	7.5	20.5	31.5	-35.5	-56.5	-68.5	140
82.5	65.5	-39.5	38.5	1.5	12.5	9.5	6.5	11.5	18.5	-18.5	59.5	-45.5	-62.5	140
-63.5	-52.5	52.5	33.5	19.5	3.5	14.5	17.5	4.5	0.5	-13.5	-32.5	72.5	83.5	140
84.5	-53.5	-33.5	32.5	22.5	-1.5	25.5	-7.5	24.5	-3.5	-12.5	53.5	73.5	-64.5	140
-65.5	74.5	54.5	35.5	40.5	-19.5	-21.5	-8.5	29.5	-10.5	34.5	-34.5	-54.5	85.5	140
86.5	-55.5	-31.5	-25.5	44.5	-23.5	42.5	46.5	56.5	-37.5	58.5	-30.5	75.5	-66.5	140
-67.5	-50.5	-60.5	79.5	-58.5	77.5	81.5	60.5	-41.5	62.5	-43.5	64.5	-51.5	87.5	140
-75.5	100.5	-79.5	98.5	-77.5	96.5	-87.5	101.5	-73.5	92.5	-71.5	90.5	-69.5	94.5	140
140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{14} = \frac{4 \times 140}{14} = 40$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{14} = \frac{6 \times 140}{14} = 60$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{14} = \frac{8 \times 140}{14} = 80$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10n}{14} = \frac{10 \times 140}{14} = 100$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := \frac{12n}{14} = \frac{12 \times 140}{14} = 120$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 140.$$

Example 22. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 14 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 195, 196\}$, the magic sum is 1379. Considering $n = 1379$ in (8), we get **positive entries nested magic square** of order 14 given by

14	8	188	10	186	12	196	7	182	16	180	18	178	184	1379
195	160	169	29	167	31	27	48	150	46	152	44	159	2	1379
3	42	139	134	64	132	66	62	52	146	50	140	155	194	1379
193	41	61	74	68	128	130	117	79	119	73	136	156	4	1379
5	157	137	71	112	110	83	116	84	86	126	60	40	192	1379
191	158	59	72	82	104	91	94	105	115	125	138	39	6	1379
177	165	144	77	88	97	102	99	96	109	120	53	32	20	1379
171	154	49	127	90	101	98	95	100	107	70	148	43	26	1379
25	36	141	122	108	92	103	106	93	89	75	56	161	172	1379
173	35	55	121	111	87	114	81	113	85	76	142	162	24	1379
23	163	143	124	129	69	67	80	118	78	123	54	34	174	1379
175	33	57	63	133	65	131	135	145	51	147	58	164	22	1379
21	38	28	168	30	166	170	149	47	151	45	153	37	176	1379
13	189	9	187	11	185	1	190	15	181	17	179	19	183	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{14} = \frac{4 \times 1379}{14} = 394$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{14} = \frac{6 \times 1379}{14} = 591$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{14} = \frac{8 \times 1379}{14} = 788$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10n}{14} = \frac{10 \times 1379}{14} = 985$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := \frac{12n}{14} = \frac{12 \times 1379}{14} = 1182$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 1379.$$

2.8 Nested Magic Square of Order 13

Result 8. Nested magic square of order 13 with *symmetric entries* and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by

$71+n/13$	$62+n/13$	$64+n/13$	$66+n/13$	$68+n/13$	$70+n/13$	$72+n/13$	$-76+n/13$	$-78+n/13$	$-80+n/13$	$-82+n/13$	$-84+n/13$	$-73+n/13$
$-83+n/13$	$-49+n/13$	$-41+n/13$	$-43+n/13$	$-45+n/13$	$-47+n/13$	$52+n/13$	$53+n/13$	$55+n/13$	$57+n/13$	$59+n/13$	$-51+n/13$	$83+n/13$
$-81+n/13$	$60+n/13$	$-33+n/13$	$39+n/13$	$37+n/13$	$35+n/13$	$34+n/13$	$-29+n/13$	$-27+n/13$	$-25+n/13$	$-31+n/13$	$-60+n/13$	$81+n/13$
$-79+n/13$	$58+n/13$	$-40+n/13$	$-17+n/13$	$-13+n/13$	$-15+n/13$	$20+n/13$	$21+n/13$	$23+n/13$	$-19+n/13$	$40+n/13$	$-58+n/13$	$79+n/13$
$-77+n/13$	$56+n/13$	$-38+n/13$	$24+n/13$	$-9+n/13$	$-12+n/13$	$8+n/13$	$6+n/13$	$7+n/13$	$-24+n/13$	$38+n/13$	$-56+n/13$	$77+n/13$
$-75+n/13$	$54+n/13$	$-36+n/13$	$22+n/13$	$11+n/13$	$1+n/13$	$-4+n/13$	$3+n/13$	$-11+n/13$	$-22+n/13$	$36+n/13$	$-54+n/13$	$75+n/13$
$-74+n/13$	$-50+n/13$	$32+n/13$	$-18+n/13$	$10+n/13$	$2+n/13$	$0+n/13$	$-2+n/13$	$-10+n/13$	$18+n/13$	$-32+n/13$	$50+n/13$	$74+n/13$
$69+n/13$	$-48+n/13$	$30+n/13$	$-16+n/13$	$-5+n/13$	$-3+n/13$	$4+n/13$	$-1+n/13$	$5+n/13$	$16+n/13$	$-30+n/13$	$48+n/13$	$-69+n/13$
$67+n/13$	$-46+n/13$	$28+n/13$	$-14+n/13$	$-7+n/13$	$12+n/13$	$-8+n/13$	$-6+n/13$	$9+n/13$	$14+n/13$	$-28+n/13$	$46+n/13$	$-67+n/13$
$65+n/13$	$-44+n/13$	$26+n/13$	$19+n/13$	$13+n/13$	$15+n/13$	$-20+n/13$	$-21+n/13$	$-23+n/13$	$17+n/13$	$-26+n/13$	$44+n/13$	$-65+n/13$
$63+n/13$	$-42+n/13$	$31+n/13$	$-39+n/13$	$-37+n/13$	$-35+n/13$	$-34+n/13$	$29+n/13$	$27+n/13$	$25+n/13$	$33+n/13$	$42+n/13$	$-63+n/13$
$61+n/13$	$51+n/13$	$41+n/13$	$43+n/13$	$45+n/13$	$47+n/13$	$-52+n/13$	$-53+n/13$	$-55+n/13$	$-57+n/13$	$-59+n/13$	$49+n/13$	$-61+n/13$
$73+n/13$	$-62+n/13$	$-64+n/13$	$-66+n/13$	$-68+n/13$	$-70+n/13$	$-72+n/13$	$76+n/13$	$78+n/13$	$80+n/13$	$82+n/13$	$84+n/13$	$-71+n/13$
n												

(9)

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{13}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{13}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{13}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{13}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{13}$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := n$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm 83, \pm 84\}$.

Example 23. Let's consider $n = 141$ in (9), we get

81 11/13	72 11/13	74 11/13	76 11/13	78 11/13	80 11/13	82 11/13	-65 2/13	-67 2/13	-69 2/13	-71 2/13	-73 2/13	-62 2/13	141
-72 2/13	-38 2/13	-30 2/13	-32 2/13	-34 2/13	-36 2/13	62 11/13	63 11/13	65 11/13	67 11/13	69 11/13	-40 2/13	93 11/13	141
-70 2/13	70 11/13	-22 2/13	49 11/13	47 11/13	45 11/13	44 11/13	-18 2/13	-16 2/13	-14 2/13	-20 2/13	-49 2/13	91 11/13	141
-68 2/13	68 11/13	-29 2/13	-6 2/13	-2 2/13	-4 2/13	30 11/13	31 11/13	33 11/13	-8 2/13	50 11/13	-47 2/13	89 11/13	141
-66 2/13	66 11/13	-27 2/13	34 11/13	11 11/13	-1 2/13	18 11/13	16 11/13	17 11/13	-13 2/13	48 11/13	-45 2/13	87 11/13	141
-64 2/13	64 11/13	-25 2/13	32 11/13	21 11/13	11 11/13	6 11/13	13 11/13	- 2/13	-11 2/13	46 11/13	-43 2/13	85 11/13	141
-63 2/13	-39 2/13	42 11/13	-7 2/13	20 11/13	12 11/13	10 11/13	8 11/13	11/13	28 11/13	-21 2/13	60 11/13	84 11/13	141
79 11/13	-37 2/13	40 11/13	-5 2/13	5 11/13	7 11/13	14 11/13	9 11/13	15 11/13	26 11/13	-19 2/13	58 11/13	-58 2/13	141
77 11/13	-35 2/13	38 11/13	-3 2/13	3 11/13	22 11/13	2 11/13	4 11/13	19 11/13	24 11/13	-17 2/13	56 11/13	-56 2/13	141
75 11/13	-33 2/13	36 11/13	29 11/13	23 11/13	25 11/13	-9 2/13	-10 2/13	-12 2/13	27 11/13	-15 2/13	54 11/13	-54 2/13	141
73 11/13	-31 2/13	41 11/13	-28 2/13	-26 2/13	-24 2/13	-23 2/13	39 11/13	37 11/13	35 11/13	43 11/13	52 11/13	-52 2/13	141
71 11/13	61 11/13	51 11/13	53 11/13	55 11/13	57 11/13	-41 2/13	-42 2/13	-44 2/13	-46 2/13	-48 2/13	59 11/13	-50 2/13	141
83 11/13	-51 2/13	-53 2/13	-55 2/13	-57 2/13	-59 2/13	-61 2/13	86 11/13	88 11/13	90 11/13	92 11/13	94 11/13	-60 2/13	141
141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141	141

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{13} = \frac{3 \times 141}{13} = \frac{423}{13}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{13} = \frac{5 \times 141}{13} = \frac{705}{13}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{13} = \frac{7 \times 141}{13} = \frac{987}{13}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{13} = \frac{9 \times 141}{13} = \frac{1269}{13}$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{13} = \frac{11 \times 141}{13} = \frac{1551}{13}$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 141.$$

Example 24. Let's consider $n = 143$ in (9), we get

82	73	75	77	79	81	83	-65	-67	-69	-71	-73	-62	143
-72	-38	-30	-32	-34	-36	63	64	66	68	70	-40	94	143
-70	71	-22	50	48	46	45	-18	-16	-14	-20	-49	92	143
-68	69	-29	-6	-2	-4	31	32	34	-8	51	-47	90	143
-66	67	-27	35	2	-1	19	17	18	-13	49	-45	88	143
-64	65	-25	33	22	12	7	14	0	-11	47	-43	86	143
-63	-39	43	-7	21	13	11	9	1	29	-21	61	85	143
80	-37	41	-5	6	8	15	10	16	27	-19	59	-58	143
78	-35	39	-3	4	23	3	5	20	25	-17	57	-56	143
76	-33	37	30	24	26	-9	-10	-12	28	-15	55	-54	143
74	-31	42	-28	-26	-24	-23	40	38	36	44	53	-52	143
72	62	52	54	56	58	-41	-42	-44	-46	-48	60	-50	143
84	-51	-53	-55	-57	-59	-61	87	89	91	93	95	-60	143
143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{13} = \frac{3 \times 143}{13} = 33$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{13} = \frac{5 \times 143}{13} = 55$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{13} = \frac{7 \times 143}{13} = 77$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{13} = \frac{9 \times 143}{13} = 99$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{13} = \frac{11 \times 143}{13} = 121$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 143.$$

Example 25. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 13 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 168, 169\}$, the magic sum is 1105. Considering $n = 1105$ in (9), we get *positive entries nested magic square* of order 13 given by

156	147	149	151	153	155	157	9	7	5	3	1	12	1105
2	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	168	1105
4	145	52	124	122	120	119	56	58	60	54	25	166	1105
6	143	45	68	72	70	105	106	108	66	125	27	164	1105
8	141	47	109	76	73	93	91	92	61	123	29	162	1105
10	139	49	107	96	86	81	88	74	63	121	31	160	1105
11	35	117	67	95	87	85	83	75	103	53	135	159	1105
154	37	115	69	80	82	89	84	90	101	55	133	16	1105
152	39	113	71	78	97	77	79	94	99	57	131	18	1105
150	41	111	104	98	100	65	64	62	102	59	129	20	1105
148	43	116	46	48	50	51	114	112	110	118	127	22	1105
146	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	24	1105
158	23	21	19	17	15	13	161	163	165	167	169	14	1105
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{13} = \frac{3 \times 1105}{13} = 255$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{13} = \frac{5 \times 1105}{13} = 425$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{13} = \frac{7 \times 1105}{13} = 595$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{13} = \frac{9 \times 1105}{13} = 765$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := \frac{11n}{13} = \frac{11 \times 1105}{13} = 935$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 1105.$$

2.9 Nested Magic Square of Order 12

Result 9. Nested magic square of order 12 with *symmetric entries* and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by

$61.5+n/12$	$70.5+n/12$	$-69.5+n/12$	$68.5+n/12$	$-67.5+n/12$	$-71.5+n/12$	$-50.5+n/12$	$51.5+n/12$	$-52.5+n/12$	$53.5+n/12$	$-54.5+n/12$	$60.5+n/12$	n
$-56.5+n/12$	$40.5+n/12$	$35.5+n/12$	$-34.5+n/12$	$33.5+n/12$	$-32.5+n/12$	$-36.5+n/12$	$-46.5+n/12$	$47.5+n/12$	$-48.5+n/12$	$41.5+n/12$	$56.5+n/12$	n
$-57.5+n/12$	$-37.5+n/12$	$-24.5+n/12$	$-30.5+n/12$	$29.5+n/12$	$31.5+n/12$	$18.5+n/12$	$-19.5+n/12$	$20.5+n/12$	$-25.5+n/12$	$37.5+n/12$	$57.5+n/12$	n
$58.5+n/12$	$38.5+n/12$	$-27.5+n/12$	$13.5+n/12$	$11.5+n/12$	$-15.5+n/12$	$17.5+n/12$	$-14.5+n/12$	$-12.5+n/12$	$27.5+n/12$	$-38.5+n/12$	$-58.5+n/12$	n
$59.5+n/12$	$-39.5+n/12$	$-26.5+n/12$	$-16.5+n/12$	$5.5+n/12$	$-7.5+n/12$	$-4.5+n/12$	$6.5+n/12$	$16.5+n/12$	$26.5+n/12$	$39.5+n/12$	$-59.5+n/12$	n
$66.5+n/12$	$45.5+n/12$	$-21.5+n/12$	$-10.5+n/12$	$-1.5+n/12$	$3.5+n/12$	$0.5+n/12$	$-2.5+n/12$	$10.5+n/12$	$21.5+n/12$	$-45.5+n/12$	$-66.5+n/12$	n
$55.5+n/12$	$-49.5+n/12$	$28.5+n/12$	$-8.5+n/12$	$2.5+n/12$	$-0.5+n/12$	$-3.5+n/12$	$1.5+n/12$	$8.5+n/12$	$-28.5+n/12$	$49.5+n/12$	$-55.5+n/12$	n
$-62.5+n/12$	$42.5+n/12$	$23.5+n/12$	$9.5+n/12$	$-6.5+n/12$	$4.5+n/12$	$7.5+n/12$	$-5.5+n/12$	$-9.5+n/12$	$-23.5+n/12$	$-42.5+n/12$	$62.5+n/12$	n
$-63.5+n/12$	$-43.5+n/12$	$22.5+n/12$	$12.5+n/12$	$-11.5+n/12$	$15.5+n/12$	$-17.5+n/12$	$14.5+n/12$	$-13.5+n/12$	$-22.5+n/12$	$43.5+n/12$	$63.5+n/12$	n
$64.5+n/12$	$44.5+n/12$	$25.5+n/12$	$30.5+n/12$	$-29.5+n/12$	$-31.5+n/12$	$-18.5+n/12$	$19.5+n/12$	$-20.5+n/12$	$24.5+n/12$	$-44.5+n/12$	$-64.5+n/12$	n
$-65.5+n/12$	$-41.5+n/12$	$-35.5+n/12$	$34.5+n/12$	$-33.5+n/12$	$32.5+n/12$	$36.5+n/12$	$46.5+n/12$	$-47.5+n/12$	$48.5+n/12$	$-40.5+n/12$	$65.5+n/12$	n
$-60.5+n/12$	$-70.5+n/12$	$69.5+n/12$	$-68.5+n/12$	$67.5+n/12$	$71.5+n/12$	$50.5+n/12$	$-51.5+n/12$	$52.5+n/12$	$-53.5+n/12$	$54.5+n/12$	$-61.5+n/12$	n
n	n											

(10)

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= \frac{4n}{12} = \frac{n}{3} & S_{10 \times 10} &:= \frac{10n}{12} = \frac{5n}{6} \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= \frac{6n}{12} = \frac{n}{2} & S_{12 \times 12} &:= \frac{12n}{12} = n. \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= \frac{8n}{12} = \frac{2n}{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{\pm 0.5, \pm 1.5, \dots, \pm 70.5 \pm 71.5\}$.

Example 26. Let's consider $n = 133$ in (10), we get

72 7/12	81 7/12	-58 5/12	79 7/12	-56 5/12	-60 5/12	-39 5/12	62 7/12	-41 5/12	64 7/12	-43 5/12	71 7/12	133
-45 5/12	51 7/12	46 7/12	-23 5/12	44 7/12	-21 5/12	-25 5/12	-35 5/12	58 7/12	-37 5/12	52 7/12	67 7/12	133
-46 5/12	-26 5/12	-13 5/12	-19 5/12	40 7/12	42 7/12	29 7/12	-8 5/12	31 7/12	-14 5/12	48 7/12	68 7/12	133
69 7/12	49 7/12	-16 5/12	24 7/12	22 7/12	-4 5/12	28 7/12	-3 5/12	-1 5/12	38 7/12	-27 5/12	-47 5/12	133
70 7/12	-28 5/12	-15 5/12	-5 5/12	16 7/12	3 7/12	6 7/12	17 7/12	27 7/12	37 7/12	50 7/12	-48 5/12	133
77 7/12	56 7/12	-10 5/12	7/12	9 7/12	14 7/12	11 7/12	8 7/12	21 7/12	32 7/12	-34 5/12	-55 5/12	133
66 7/12	-38 5/12	39 7/12	2 7/12	13 7/12	10 7/12	7 7/12	12 7/12	19 7/12	-17 5/12	60 7/12	-44 5/12	133
-51 5/12	53 7/12	34 7/12	20 7/12	4 7/12	15 7/12	18 7/12	5 7/12	1 7/12	-12 5/12	-31 5/12	73 7/12	133
-52 5/12	-32 5/12	33 7/12	23 7/12	-5 5/12	26 7/12	-6 5/12	25 7/12	-2 5/12	-11 5/12	54 7/12	74 7/12	133
75 7/12	55 7/12	36 7/12	41 7/12	-18 5/12	-20 5/12	-7 5/12	30 7/12	-9 5/12	35 7/12	-33 5/12	-53 5/12	133
-54 5/12	-30 5/12	-24 5/12	45 7/12	-22 5/12	43 7/12	47 7/12	57 7/12	-36 5/12	59 7/12	-29 5/12	76 7/12	133
-49 5/12	-59 5/12	80 7/12	-57 5/12	78 7/12	82 7/12	61 7/12	-40 5/12	63 7/12	-42 5/12	65 7/12	-50 5/12	133
133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{12} = \frac{4 \times 133}{12} = \frac{133}{3}$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{12} = \frac{6 \times 133}{12} = \frac{133}{2}$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{12} = \frac{8 \times 133}{12} = \frac{266}{3}$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10n}{12} = \frac{10 \times 133}{12} = \frac{665}{6}$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 133.$$

Example 27. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 12 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 63, 143, 144\}$, the magic sum is 870. Considering $n = 870$ in (10), we get **positive entries nested magic square** of order 12 given by

134	143	3	141	5	1	22	124	20	126	18	133	870
16	113	108	38	106	40	36	26	120	24	114	129	870
15	35	48	42	102	104	91	53	93	47	110	130	870
131	111	45	86	84	57	90	58	60	100	34	14	870
132	33	46	56	78	65	68	79	89	99	112	13	870
139	118	51	62	71	76	73	70	83	94	27	6	870
128	23	101	64	75	72	69	74	81	44	122	17	870
10	115	96	82	66	77	80	67	63	49	30	135	870
9	29	95	85	61	88	55	87	59	50	116	136	870
137	117	98	103	43	41	54	92	52	97	28	8	870
7	31	37	107	39	105	109	119	25	121	32	138	870
12	2	142	4	140	144	123	21	125	19	127	11	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{12} = \frac{4 \times 870}{12} = 290$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{12} = \frac{6 \times 870}{12} = 435$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{12} = \frac{8 \times 870}{12} = 580$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10n}{12} = \frac{10 \times 870}{12} = 725$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 870.$$

2.10 Nested Magic Square of Order 11

Result 10. Nested magic square of order 11 with *symmetric entries* and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by

$-49+n/11$	$-41+n/11$	$-43+n/11$	$-45+n/11$	$-47+n/11$	$52+n/11$	$53+n/11$	$55+n/11$	$57+n/11$	$59+n/11$	$-51+n/11$	n
$60+n/11$	$-33+n/11$	$39+n/11$	$37+n/11$	$35+n/11$	$34+n/11$	$-29+n/11$	$-27+n/11$	$-25+n/11$	$-31+n/11$	$-60+n/11$	n
$58+n/11$	$-40+n/11$	$-17+n/11$	$-13+n/11$	$-15+n/11$	$20+n/11$	$21+n/11$	$23+n/11$	$-19+n/11$	$40+n/11$	$-58+n/11$	n
$56+n/11$	$-38+n/11$	$24+n/11$	$-9+n/11$	$-12+n/11$	$8+n/11$	$6+n/11$	$7+n/11$	$-24+n/11$	$38+n/11$	$-56+n/11$	n
$54+n/11$	$-36+n/11$	$22+n/11$	$11+n/11$	$1+n/11$	$-4+n/11$	$3+n/11$	$-11+n/11$	$-22+n/11$	$36+n/11$	$-54+n/11$	n
$-50+n/11$	$32+n/11$	$-18+n/11$	$10+n/11$	$2+n/11$	$0+n/11$	$-2+n/11$	$-10+n/11$	$18+n/11$	$-32+n/11$	$50+n/11$	n
$-48+n/11$	$30+n/11$	$-16+n/11$	$-5+n/11$	$-3+n/11$	$4+n/11$	$-1+n/11$	$5+n/11$	$16+n/11$	$-30+n/11$	$48+n/11$	n
$-46+n/11$	$28+n/11$	$-14+n/11$	$-7+n/11$	$12+n/11$	$-8+n/11$	$-6+n/11$	$9+n/11$	$14+n/11$	$-28+n/11$	$46+n/11$	n
$-44+n/11$	$26+n/11$	$19+n/11$	$13+n/11$	$15+n/11$	$-20+n/11$	$-21+n/11$	$-23+n/11$	$17+n/11$	$-26+n/11$	$44+n/11$	n
$-42+n/11$	$31+n/11$	$-39+n/11$	$-37+n/11$	$-35+n/11$	$-34+n/11$	$29+n/11$	$27+n/11$	$25+n/11$	$33+n/11$	$42+n/11$	n
$51+n/11$	$41+n/11$	$43+n/11$	$45+n/11$	$47+n/11$	$-52+n/11$	$-53+n/11$	$-55+n/11$	$-57+n/11$	$-59+n/11$	$49+n/11$	n
n	n										

(11)

In this case, the magic sums are given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= \frac{3n}{11} \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= \frac{5n}{11} \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= \frac{7n}{11} \\
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= \frac{9n}{11} \\
 S_{11 \times 11} &:= n
 \end{aligned}$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm 59, \pm 60\}$.

Example 28. Let's consider $n = 143$ in (11), we get

-36	-28	-30	-32	-34	65	66	68	70	72	-38	143
73	-20	52	50	48	47	-16	-14	-12	-18	-47	143
71	-27	-4	0	-2	33	34	36	-6	53	-45	143
69	-25	37	4	1	21	19	20	-11	51	-43	143
67	-23	35	24	14	9	16	2	-9	49	-41	143
-37	45	-5	23	15	13	11	3	31	-19	63	143
-35	43	-3	8	10	17	12	18	29	-17	61	143
-33	41	-1	6	25	5	7	22	27	-15	59	143
-31	39	32	26	28	-7	-8	-10	30	-13	57	143
-29	44	-26	-24	-22	-21	42	40	38	46	55	143
64	54	56	58	60	-39	-40	-42	-44	-46	62	143
143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143	143

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{11} = \frac{3 \times 143}{11} = 39$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{11} = \frac{5 \times 143}{11} = 65$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{11} = \frac{7 \times 143}{11} = 91$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{11} = \frac{9 \times 143}{11} = 117$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 143.$$

Example 29. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 11 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 120, 121\}$, the magic sum is 671. Considering $n = 671$ in (11), we get **positive entries nested magic square** of order 11 given by

12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671
121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1	671
119	21	44	48	46	81	82	84	42	101	3	671
117	23	85	52	49	69	67	68	37	99	5	671
115	25	83	72	62	57	64	50	39	97	7	671
11	93	43	71	63	61	59	51	79	29	111	671
13	91	45	56	58	65	60	66	77	31	109	671
15	89	47	54	73	53	55	70	75	33	107	671
17	87	80	74	76	41	40	38	78	35	105	671
19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103	671
112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{11} = \frac{3 \times 671}{11} = 183$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{11} = \frac{5 \times 671}{11} = 305$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{11} = \frac{7 \times 671}{11} = 437$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9n}{11} = \frac{9 \times 671}{11} = 549$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 671.$$

2.11 Nested Magic Square of Order 10

Result 11. *Nested magic square of order 10 with symmetric entries and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by*

$40.5+n$	$35.5+n$	$-34.5+n$	$33.5+n$	$-32.5+n$	$-36.5+n$	$-46.5+n$	$47.5+n$	$-48.5+n$	$41.5+n$	n
$-37.5+n$	$-24.5+n$	$-30.5+n$	$29.5+n$	$31.5+n$	$18.5+n$	$-19.5+n$	$20.5+n$	$-25.5+n$	$37.5+n$	n
$38.5+n$	$-27.5+n$	$13.5+n$	$11.5+n$	$-15.5+n$	$17.5+n$	$-14.5+n$	$-12.5+n$	$27.5+n$	$-38.5+n$	n
$-39.5+n$	$-26.5+n$	$-16.5+n$	$5.5+n$	$-7.5+n$	$-4.5+n$	$6.5+n$	$16.5+n$	$26.5+n$	$39.5+n$	n
$45.5+n$	$-21.5+n$	$-10.5+n$	$-1.5+n$	$3.5+n$	$0.5+n$	$-2.5+n$	$10.5+n$	$21.5+n$	$-45.5+n$	n
$-49.5+n$	$28.5+n$	$-8.5+n$	$2.5+n$	$-0.5+n$	$-3.5+n$	$1.5+n$	$8.5+n$	$-28.5+n$	$49.5+n$	n
$42.5+n$	$23.5+n$	$9.5+n$	$-6.5+n$	$4.5+n$	$7.5+n$	$-5.5+n$	$-9.5+n$	$-23.5+n$	$-42.5+n$	n
$-43.5+n$	$22.5+n$	$12.5+n$	$-11.5+n$	$15.5+n$	$-17.5+n$	$14.5+n$	$-13.5+n$	$-22.5+n$	$43.5+n$	n
$44.5+n$	$25.5+n$	$30.5+n$	$-29.5+n$	$-31.5+n$	$-18.5+n$	$19.5+n$	$-20.5+n$	$24.5+n$	$-44.5+n$	n
$-41.5+n$	$-35.5+n$	$34.5+n$	$-33.5+n$	$32.5+n$	$36.5+n$	$46.5+n$	$-47.5+n$	$48.5+n$	$-40.5+n$	n
n	n									

(12)

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{10} = \frac{2n}{5}$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{10} = \frac{3n}{5}$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{10} = \frac{4n}{5}$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10n}{10} = n.$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{\pm 0.5, \pm 1.5, \dots, \pm 48.5 \pm 49.5\}$.

Example 30. Let's consider $n = 132$ in (12), we get

53.7	48.7	-21.3	46.7	-19.3	-23.3	-33.3	60.7	-35.3	54.7	132
-24.3	-11.3	-17.3	42.7	44.7	31.7	-6.3	33.7	-12.3	50.7	132
51.7	-14.3	26.7	24.7	-2.3	30.7	-1.3	0.7	40.7	-25.3	132
-26.3	-13.3	-3.3	18.7	5.7	8.7	19.7	29.7	39.7	52.7	132
58.7	-8.3	2.7	11.7	16.7	13.7	10.7	23.7	34.7	-32.3	132
-36.3	41.7	4.7	15.7	12.7	9.7	14.7	21.7	-15.3	62.7	132
55.7	36.7	22.7	6.7	17.7	20.7	7.7	3.7	-10.3	-29.3	132
-30.3	35.7	25.7	1.7	28.7	-4.3	27.7	-0.3	-9.3	56.7	132
57.7	38.7	43.7	-16.3	-18.3	-5.3	32.7	-7.3	37.7	-31.3	132
-28.3	-22.3	47.7	-20.3	45.7	49.7	59.7	-34.3	61.7	-27.3	132
132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{10} = \frac{4 \times 132}{10} = 52.8$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{10} = \frac{6 \times 132}{10} = 79.2$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{10} = \frac{8 \times 132}{10} = 105.6$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 132.$$

Example 31. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 10 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 63, 99, 100\}$, the magic sum is 505. Considering $n = 505$ in (12), we get **positive entries nested magic square** of order 10 given by

91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92	505
13	26	20	80	82	69	31	71	25	88	505
89	23	64	62	35	68	36	38	78	12	505
11	24	34	56	43	46	57	67	77	90	505
96	29	40	49	54	51	48	61	72	5	505
1	79	42	53	50	47	52	59	22	100	505
93	74	60	44	55	58	45	41	27	8	505
7	73	63	39	66	33	65	37	28	94	505
95	76	81	21	19	32	70	30	75	6	505
9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{10} = \frac{4 \times 505}{10} = 202$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{10} = \frac{6 \times 505}{10} = 303$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{10} = \frac{6 \times 505}{10} = 404$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 505.$$

2.12 Nested Magic Square of Order 9

Result 12. Nested magic square of order 9 with **symmetric entries** and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by

$-33+n/9$	$39+n/9$	$37+n/9$	$35+n/9$	$34+n/9$	$-29+n/9$	$-27+n/9$	$-25+n/9$	$-31+n/9$	n
$-40+n/9$	$-17+n/9$	$-13+n/9$	$-15+n/9$	$20+n/9$	$21+n/9$	$23+n/9$	$-19+n/9$	$40+n/9$	n
$-38+n/9$	$24+n/9$	$-9+n/9$	$-12+n/9$	$8+n/9$	$6+n/9$	$7+n/9$	$-24+n/9$	$38+n/9$	n
$-36+n/9$	$22+n/9$	$11+n/9$	$1+n/9$	$-4+n/9$	$3+n/9$	$-11+n/9$	$-22+n/9$	$36+n/9$	n
$32+n/9$	$-18+n/9$	$10+n/9$	$2+n/9$	$0+n/9$	$-2+n/9$	$-10+n/9$	$18+n/9$	$-32+n/9$	n
$30+n/9$	$-16+n/9$	$-5+n/9$	$-3+n/9$	$4+n/9$	$-1+n/9$	$5+n/9$	$16+n/9$	$-30+n/9$	n
$28+n/9$	$-14+n/9$	$-7+n/9$	$12+n/9$	$-8+n/9$	$-6+n/9$	$9+n/9$	$14+n/9$	$-28+n/9$	n
$26+n/9$	$19+n/9$	$13+n/9$	$15+n/9$	$-20+n/9$	$-21+n/9$	$-23+n/9$	$17+n/9$	$-26+n/9$	n
$31+n/9$	$-39+n/9$	$-37+n/9$	$-35+n/9$	$-34+n/9$	$29+n/9$	$27+n/9$	$25+n/9$	$33+n/9$	n
n	n								

(13)

In this case, the magic sums are given by,

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 3n/9$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 7n/9$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 5n/9$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := n,$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm 39, \pm 40\}$.

Example 32. Let's consider $n = 135$ in (13), we get

-18	54	52	50	49	-14	-12	-10	-16	135
-25	-2	2	0	35	36	38	-4	55	135
-23	39	6	3	23	21	22	-9	53	135
-21	37	26	16	11	18	4	-7	51	135
47	-3	25	17	15	13	5	33	-17	135
45	-1	10	12	19	14	20	31	-15	135
43	1	8	27	7	9	24	29	-13	135
41	34	28	30	-5	-6	-8	32	-11	135
46	-24	-22	-20	-19	44	42	40	48	135
135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{9} = \frac{3 \times 135}{9} = 45$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{9} = \frac{5 \times 135}{9} = 75$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{9} = \frac{7 \times 135}{9} = 105$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 135.$$

Since the number 135 is divisible by 9, the magic sums are integers. Specially, in this case all are positive numbers.

Example 33. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 9 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 80, 81\}$, the magic sum is 369. Considering $n = 369$ in (13), we get *positive entries nested magic square of order 9* given by

8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10	369
1	24	28	26	61	62	64	22	81	369
3	65	32	29	49	47	48	17	79	369
5	63	52	42	37	44	30	19	77	369
73	23	51	43	41	39	31	59	9	369
71	25	36	38	45	40	46	57	11	369
69	27	34	53	33	35	50	55	13	369
67	60	54	56	21	20	18	58	15	369
72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74	369
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{9} = \frac{3 \times 369}{9} = 123$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{9} = \frac{5 \times 369}{9} = 205$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := \frac{7n}{9} = \frac{7 \times 369}{9} = 287$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 369.$$

2.13 Nested Magic Square Order of 8

Result 13. *Nested magic square of order 8 with symmetric entries and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by*

$-24.5+.125n$	$-30.5+.125n$	$29.5+.125n$	$31.5+.125n$	$18.5+.125n$	$-19.5+.125n$	$20.5+.125n$	$-25.5+.125n$	n
$-27.5+.125n$	$13.5+.125n$	$11.5+.125n$	$-15.5+.125n$	$17.5+.125n$	$-14.5+.125n$	$-12.5+.125n$	$27.5+.125n$	n
$-26.5+.125n$	$-16.5+.125n$	$5.5+.125n$	$-7.5+.125n$	$-4.5+.125n$	$6.5+.125n$	$16.5+.125n$	$26.5+.125n$	n
$-21.5+.125n$	$-10.5+.125n$	$-1.5+.125n$	$3.5+.125n$	$0.5+.125n$	$-2.5+.125n$	$10.5+.125n$	$21.5+.125n$	n
$28.5+.125n$	$-8.5+.125n$	$2.5+.125n$	$-0.5+.125n$	$-3.5+.125n$	$1.5+.125n$	$8.5+.125n$	$-28.5+.125n$	n
$23.5+.125n$	$9.5+.125n$	$-6.5+.125n$	$4.5+.125n$	$7.5+.125n$	$-5.5+.125n$	$-9.5+.125n$	$-23.5+.125n$	n
$22.5+.125n$	$12.5+.125n$	$-11.5+.125n$	$15.5+.125n$	$-17.5+.125n$	$14.5+.125n$	$-13.5+.125n$	$-22.5+.125n$	n
$25.5+.125n$	$30.5+.125n$	$-29.5+.125n$	$-31.5+.125n$	$-18.5+.125n$	$19.5+.125n$	$-20.5+.125n$	$24.5+.125n$	n
n	n							

(14)

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{8} = \frac{n}{2}$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{8} = \frac{3n}{4}$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8n}{8} = n$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{\pm 0.5, \pm 1.5, \dots, \pm 30.5 \pm 31.5\}$.

Example 34. Let's consider $n = 131$ in (14), we get

-8.125	-14.125	45.875	47.875	34.875	-3.125	36.875	-9.125	131
-11.125	29.875	27.875	0.875	33.875	1.875	3.875	43.875	131
-10.125	-0.125	21.875	8.875	11.875	22.875	32.875	42.875	131
-5.125	5.875	14.875	19.875	16.875	13.875	26.875	37.875	131
44.875	7.875	18.875	15.875	12.875	17.875	24.875	-12.125	131
39.875	25.875	9.875	20.875	23.875	10.875	6.875	-7.125	131
38.875	28.875	4.875	31.875	-1.125	30.875	2.875	-6.125	131
41.875	46.875	-13.125	-15.125	-2.125	35.875	-4.125	40.875	131
131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131	131

According to above formula, the magic sums are

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{n}{2} = \frac{131}{2} = 65.5$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3n}{4} = \frac{3 \times 131}{4} = 98.25$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 131.$$

Example 35. Let's consider $n = 137$ in (14), we get

								137
-7.375	-13.375	46.625	48.625	35.625	-2.375	37.625	-8.375	137
-10.375	30.625	28.625	1.625	34.625	2.625	4.625	44.625	137
-9.375	0.625	22.625	9.625	12.625	23.625	33.625	43.625	137
-4.375	6.625	15.625	20.625	17.625	14.625	27.625	38.625	137
45.625	8.625	19.625	16.625	13.625	18.625	25.625	-11.375	137
40.625	26.625	10.625	21.625	24.625	11.625	7.625	-6.375	137
39.625	29.625	5.625	32.625	-0.375	31.625	3.625	-5.375	137
42.625	47.625	-12.375	-14.375	-1.375	36.625	-3.375	41.625	137
137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137	137

According to above formula, the magic sums are

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{n}{2} = \frac{137}{2} = 68.5$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{3n}{4} = \frac{3 \times 137}{4} = 102.75$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 137.$$

Example 36. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 8 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 63, 64\}$, the magic sum is 260. Considering $n = 260$ in (14), we get **positive entries nested magic square** of order 8 given by

								260
8	2	62	64	51	13	53	7	260
5	46	44	17	50	18	20	60	260
6	16	38	25	28	39	49	59	260
11	22	31	36	33	30	43	54	260
61	24	35	32	29	34	41	4	260
56	42	26	37	40	27	23	9	260
55	45	21	48	15	47	19	10	260
58	63	3	1	14	52	12	57	260
260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{8} = \frac{4 \times 260}{8} = 130$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{8} = \frac{6 \times 260}{8} = 195$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 260.$$

2.14 Nested Magic Square of Order 7

Result 14. Nested magic square of order 7 with *symmetric entries* and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by

$-17+n/7$	$-13+n/7$	$-15+n/7$	$20+n/7$	$21+n/7$	$23+n/7$	$-19+n/7$	n
$24+n/7$	$-9+n/7$	$-12+n/7$	$8+n/7$	$6+n/7$	$7+n/7$	$-24+n/7$	n
$22+n/7$	$11+n/7$	$1+n/7$	$-4+n/7$	$3+n/7$	$-11+n/7$	$-22+n/7$	n
$-18+n/7$	$10+n/7$	$2+n/7$	$0+n/7$	$-2+n/7$	$-10+n/7$	$18+n/7$	n
$-16+n/7$	$-5+n/7$	$-3+n/7$	$4+n/7$	$-1+n/7$	$5+n/7$	$16+n/7$	n
$-14+n/7$	$-7+n/7$	$12+n/7$	$-8+n/7$	$-6+n/7$	$9+n/7$	$14+n/7$	n
$19+n/7$	$13+n/7$	$15+n/7$	$-20+n/7$	$-21+n/7$	$-23+n/7$	$17+n/7$	n
n	n						

(15)

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{7}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{7}$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := n.$$

For integer values magic sum, $n = \pm 7$ or 0 . For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm 23, \pm 24\}$.

Example 37. Let's consider $n = 133$ in (15), we get

							133
2	6	4	39	40	42	0	133
43	10	7	27	25	26	-5	133
41	30	20	15	22	8	-3	133
1	29	21	19	17	9	37	133
3	14	16	23	18	24	35	133
5	12	31	11	13	28	33	133
38	32	34	-1	-2	-4	36	133
133	133	133	133	133	133	133	133

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{7} = \frac{3 \times 133}{7} = 57$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{7} = \frac{5 \times 133}{7} = 95$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 133.$$

Since the number 133 is divisible by 7, the magic sums are integers. Specially, in this case all are positive numbers.

Example 38. Let's consider $n = 140$ in (15), we get

							140
3	7	5	40	41	43	1	140
44	11	8	28	26	27	-4	140
42	31	21	16	23	9	-2	140
2	30	22	20	18	10	38	140
4	15	17	24	19	25	36	140
6	13	32	12	14	29	34	140
39	33	35	0	-1	-3	37	140
140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{7} = \frac{3 \times 140}{7} = 60$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{7} = \frac{5 \times 140}{7} = 100$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 140.$$

Since the number 140 is divisible by 7, the magic sums are integers. Specially, in this case all are positive numbers.

Example 39. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 7 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 48, 49\}$, the magic sum is 175. Considering $n = 175$ in (15), we get *positive entries nested magic square* of order 7 given by

							175
42	38	40	5	4	2	44	175
1	34	37	17	19	18	49	175
3	14	24	29	22	36	47	175
43	15	23	25	27	35	7	175
41	30	28	21	26	20	9	175
39	32	13	33	31	16	11	175
6	12	10	45	46	48	8	175
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

In this case, the magic sums are

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{7} = \frac{3 \times 175}{7} = 75$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := \frac{5n}{7} = \frac{5 \times 175}{7} = 125$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 175.$$

2.15 Nested Magic Square of Order 6

Result 15. Nested magic square of order 6 with *symmetric entries* and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by

						n
$13.5+n/6$	$11.5+n/6$	$-15.5+n/6$	$17.5+n/6$	$-14.5+n/6$	$-12.5+n/6$	n
$-16.5+n/6$	$5.5+n/6$	$-7.5+n/6$	$-4.5+n/6$	$6.5+n/6$	$16.5+n/6$	n
$-10.5+n/6$	$-1.5+n/6$	$3.5+n/6$	$0.5+n/6$	$-2.5+n/6$	$10.5+n/6$	n
$-8.5+n/6$	$2.5+n/6$	$-0.5+n/6$	$-3.5+n/6$	$1.5+n/6$	$8.5+n/6$	n
$9.5+n/6$	$-6.5+n/6$	$4.5+n/6$	$7.5+n/6$	$-5.5+n/6$	$-9.5+n/6$	n
$12.5+n/6$	$-11.5+n/6$	$15.5+n/6$	$-17.5+n/6$	$14.5+n/6$	$-13.5+n/6$	n
n	n	n	n	n	n	n

(16)

In this case, the magic sums are given by,

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{6} = \frac{2n}{3}$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := \frac{6n}{6} = n.$$

For $n = 0$, the symmetric entries are $\{\pm 0.5, \pm 1.5, \dots, \pm 16.5 \pm 17.5\}$.

Example 40. Let's consider $n = 133$ in (16), we get

						133
35 2/3	33 2/3	6 2/3	39 2/3	7 2/3	9 2/3	133
5 2/3	27 2/3	14 2/3	17 2/3	28 2/3	38 2/3	133
11 2/3	20 2/3	25 2/3	22 2/3	19 2/3	32 2/3	133
13 2/3	24 2/3	21 2/3	18 2/3	23 2/3	30 2/3	133
31 2/3	15 2/3	26 2/3	29 2/3	16 2/3	12 2/3	133
34 2/3	10 2/3	37 2/3	4 2/3	36 2/3	8 2/3	133
133	133	133	133	133	133	133

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{6} = \frac{4 \times 133}{6} = \frac{266}{3}$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 133.$$

Example 41. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 6 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 35, 36\}$, the magic sum is 111. Considering $n = 111$ in (16), we get **positive entries nested magic square** of order 6 given by

						111
32	30	3	36	4	6	111
2	24	11	14	25	35	111
8	17	22	19	16	29	111
10	21	18	15	20	27	111
28	12	23	26	13	9	111
31	7	34	1	33	5	111
111	111	111	111	111	111	111

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{4 \times 4} := \frac{4n}{6} = \frac{4 \times 111}{6} = 74$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 111.$$

2.16 Nested Magic Square of Order 5

Result 16. *Nested magic square of order 5 with symmetric entries and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by*

					n
$-9+n/5$	$-12+n/5$	$8+n/5$	$6+n/5$	$7+n/5$	n
$11+n/5$	$1+n/5$	$-4+n/5$	$3+n/5$	$-11+n/5$	n
$10+n/5$	$2+n/5$	$0+n/5$	$-2+n/5$	$-10+n/5$	n
$-5+n/5$	$-3+n/5$	$4+n/5$	$-1+n/5$	$5+n/5$	n
$-7+n/5$	$12+n/5$	$-8+n/5$	$-6+n/5$	$9+n/5$	n
n	n	n	n	n	n

(17)

In this case, the magic sums are given by,

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{5}$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := n.$$

For integer values magic sum, $n = \pm 5$ or 0 . For $n = 0$, the entries are $\{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \pm 11, \pm 12\}$.

Example 42. Let's consider $n = 132$ in (17), we get

					132
17.4	14.4	34.4	32.4	33.4	132
37.4	27.4	22.4	29.4	15.4	132
36.4	28.4	26.4	24.4	16.4	132
21.4	23.4	30.4	25.4	31.4	132
19.4	38.4	18.4	20.4	35.4	132
132	132	132	132	132	132

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{5} = \frac{3 \times 132}{5} = 79.2$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 132.$$

Example 43. Let's consider $n = 135$ in (17), we get

					135
18	15	35	33	34	135
38	28	23	30	16	135
37	29	27	25	17	135
22	24	31	26	32	135
20	39	19	21	36	135
135	135	135	135	135	135

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{5} = \frac{3 \times 135}{5} = 81$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 135.$$

Since $n = 135$ is multiple of 5, this gives magic squares sum as integers. In this case, positive values.

Example 44. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 5 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 24, 25\}$, the magic sum is 65. Considering $n = 65$ in (17), we get *positive entries magic square* of order 5 given by

					65
4	1	21	19	20	65
24	14	9	16	2	65
23	15	13	11	3	65
8	10	17	12	18	65
6	25	5	7	22	65
65	65	65	65	65	65

In this case, the magic sums are given by

$$S_{3 \times 3} := \frac{3n}{5} = \frac{3 \times 65}{5} = 39$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 65.$$

2.17 Magic Square of Order 4

Result 17. Magic square of order 4 with *symmetric entries* and magic sum n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ (integer) is given by

				n
5.5+.25n	-7.5+.25n	-4.5+.25n	6.5+.25n	n
-1.5+.25n	3.5+.25n	0.5+.25n	-2.5+.25n	n
2.5+.25n	-0.5+.25n	-3.5+.25n	1.5+.25n	n
-6.5+.25n	4.5+.25n	7.5+.25n	-5.5+.25n	n
n	n	n	n	n

(18)

For $n = 0$, the entries are $\{\pm 0.5, \pm 1.5, \dots, \pm 6.5 \pm 7.5\}$.

Example 45. Let's consider $n = 131$ in above magic square of order 4, we get

				131
38.25	25.25	28.25	39.25	131
31.25	36.25	33.25	30.25	131
35.25	32.25	29.25	34.25	131
26.25	37.25	40.25	27.25	131
131	131	131	131	131

Example 46. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 4 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 15, 16\}$, the magic sum is 34. Considering $n = 34$ in (18), we get *positive entries nested magic square* of order 4 given by

				34
14	1	4	15	34
7	12	9	6	34
11	8	5	10	34
2	13	16	3	34
34	34	34	34	34

2.18 Magic Square of Order 3

Result 18. Magic square of order 3 with *symmetric entries* and magic sum n is given by

			n
$1+n/3$	$-4+n/3$	$3+n/3$	n
$2+n/3$	$0+n/3$	$-2+n/3$	n
$-3+n/3$	$4+n/3$	$-1+n/3$	n
n	n	n	n

(19)

For integer values magic sum, $n = \pm 3$ or 0. For $n = 0$, the entries are $\{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \pm 4\}$.

Example 47. Let's consider $n = 1$ in (19), we get

			1
$4/3$	$-11/3$	$10/3$	1
$7/3$	$1/3$	$-5/3$	1
$-8/3$	$13/3$	$-2/3$	1
1	1	1	1

(20)

Example 48. According to formula (1), the magic square of order 3 formed by entries $\{1, 2, \dots, 8, 9\}$, the magic sum is 15. Considering $n = 15$ in (19), we get *positive entries magic square* of order 3 given by

			15
6	1	8	15
7	5	3	15
2	9	4	15
15	15	15	15

Remark 2.1. We observe that there are three ways of getting *nested magic squares* sums. One is *whole value*, second *decimal* and third is *fractional*. It happens depending upon the choice of value of n . There are only few cases where we can get *decimal-type nested magic squares*. It happens only when nested magic squares sums multiples of 4, 5, 8 and 10. In other cases, we have either *integer* or *fractional-type nested magic squares*.

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